

University of Oxford

Conditional Diffusion Models for
Structure-Based Drug Design with
Considerations for Physical Plausibility
and a Celecoxib Rediscovery Case Study

by

Isaac Rankin

Green Templeton College

A dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the degree of Master of
Science in Statistical Sciences.

*Department of Statistics, 24–29 St Giles,
Oxford, OX1 3LB*

September 2024

This is my own work (except where otherwise indicated)

Candidate: Isaac

Rankin

Signed:

Date: *September 5th, 2024*

Abstract

Drug development is a lengthy and costly process. Extensive research and various *de novo* drug design methods are employed to identify promising compounds. Generative models can be used to find novel molecules with desired properties, however they can sometimes produce physically implausible structures. Efforts have been made to evaluate and benchmark these models. Diffusion models, known for their state-of-the-art performance in many applications, are of particular interest. This research focuses on two conditional diffusion models designed to generate molecules given a target protein pocket, and assess their quality and physical plausibility using the PoseBusters test suite. Improving the reliability of structure-based drug design models can accelerate the drug discovery process, lower development costs, and improve the chances of identifying promising compounds. Additionally, we conduct an *in silico* celecoxib rediscovery case study.

Acknowledgements

I wish to thank the following for their support and contributions:

-
-
-
-
-

Contents

List of Figures

List of Tables

1	Introduction	1
2	Background	2
3	Diffusion Generative Models	4
4	Related Models	5
5	Diffusion Models for Structure-Based Drug Design	6
5.1	Goal and Architecture of PMDM	6
5.2	Notation	7
5.3	Forward Process	8
5.4	Reverse Process	9
5.5	Cross Entropy Objective	11
5.6	Relation to Score-Based Generative Models	12
5.7	Incorporating the Protein Pocket Information	13
5.8	Training the Model	16
5.9	Sampling	17
5.10	Comparison with DiffSBDD	18
6	Methods of Assessment	20
6.1	Drug-like Properties	21
6.2	POSECHECK	21
6.3	PoseBusters	22
6.4	GuacaMol	22
7	PoseBusters Busters	24
8	PMDM Assessment	29
9	DiffSBDD Assessment	35
10	Celecoxib Rediscovery Case Study	40
11	Discussion	46
12	Conclusion	48
	Bibliography	49
	Appendices	57
A	Select Code	57

B	Glossary of Acronyms and Terms	59
C	Notation Reference Guide	60
D	Table of Common Molecular Descriptors	61
E	Forward Process Proofs	62
F	Reverse Process Proofs	66
G	Cross Entropy Proof	73
H	PoseBusters Test Suite	75
I	Missing PMDM-Generated Molecules	77
J	Celecoxib Rediscovery Plots	78
J.1	Tanimoto Similarity to Celecoxib Plots	78
J.2	1OQ5 Plots	79
J.3	3KK6 Plots	80
J.4	6COX Plots	81
J.5	7ZEJ Plots	82
J.6	Descriptor Correlation Plots	83

List of Figures

1	Overview of generative tasks, generative strategies, and molecular representations. Figure from Du <i>et al.</i> [22].	3
2	Examples of generating molecules in three different protein pockets for structure-based drug design. Molecules generated with DiffSBDD.	5
3	PMDM architecture. Figure from Huang <i>et al.</i> [39].	6
4	Ligand diffused in pocket. Figure adapted from Huang <i>et al.</i> [39].	7
5	Linear, cosine, sigmoid, and polynomial variance schedules. Figure inspired by Nichol <i>et al.</i> [59].	8
6	Discrete and continuous convolution layers. Figure from Schütt <i>et al.</i> [74].	14
7	Local and global edge construction. Figure from Huang <i>et al.</i> [39].	14
8	Analyzing the physical plausibility of the PMDM and DiffSBDD-generated molecules using PoseBusters. PB Ghost from Python package.	20
9	PoseBusters identifies physically implausible molecules. Example: molecules generated by DiffSBDD clash with proteins.	22
10	PoseBusters v0.3.1 release and InChI conversion test function.	24
11	Molecule does not sanitize: Explicit valence for atom #x N is greater than permitted	25
12	Waterfall plots comparing PoseBusters test results for PMDM-generated molecules for the 1JN2 protein.	27
13	Waterfall plots comparing PoseBusters test results for PMDM-generated molecules for the 3U5Y protein.	28
14	The PMDM-generated molecules are far from their PDB target proteins. .	29
15	Examples of failures that PoseBusters can detect for PMDM-generated molecules for the 2RMA target protein. Test results in Table 2.	30
16	PMDM-generated "molecules". Test results in Table 3.	32
17	PMDM PoseBusters v0.3.1 test results for 14GS, 2RMA, and 3AF2.	33
18	PMDM-generated molecules with high Silly Walks scores.	34
19	Example PB-valid DiffSBDD-generated 14GS and 3AF2-targeted molecules.	36
20	Analysis of 14GS-targeted DiffSBDD-generated molecules.	37
21	Analysis of 3AF2-targeted DiffSBDD-generated molecules.	38
22	Correlation between molecular descriptors for DiffSBDD-generated molecules targeting the 14GS and 3AF2 protein pockets.	39
23	Celecoxib to be rediscovered	40
24	Celecoxib and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 1OQ5	42
25	Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 1OQ5 protein pocket	43
26	Celecoxib and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 3KK6	44
27	$C_{16}H_{11}BrF_3N_3O_2S$ and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 6COX	44
28	Celecoxib and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 7ZEJ	45
29	Tanimoto similarities to Celecoxib	78
30	Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 1OQ5 protein pocket	79
31	Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 3KK6 protein pocket	80
32	Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 6COX protein pocket	81
33	Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 7ZEJ protein pocket	82
34	Correlation between molecular descriptors	83

List of Tables

1	Molecule does not sanitize: Explicit valence for atom #x N is greater than permitted	25
2	Types of PoseBusters test failures for PMDM-generated molecules targeting 2RMA for Figure 15.	31
3	PoseBusters test results for Figure 16.	32
4	Molecular Properties in Celecoxib Case Study	41
5	Glossary of Acronyms and Terms	59
6	Mathematical Notation	60
7	Common Molecular Descriptors	61
8	Description of the checks used in the PoseBusters test suite. Table from Buttenschoen <i>et al.</i> [14] and updated with InChI convertible test.	75

1 Introduction

Drugs play an essential role in modern medicine by preventing, managing, and curing a wide range of diseases, thereby improving the quality of life and extending lifespan. A drug is a chemical compound formed by atoms bonded together in a specific conformation [43]. Drugs are commonly administered orally, intravenously, or transdermally [47]. After administration, the drug must bind to a receptor on the target protein to produce a biological response as an agonist or inhibit a response as an antagonist [9]. For a molecule to be effective and safe for human use, it must not only achieve the desired therapeutic effect but also have suitable solubility, toxicity, and pharmacokinetic properties [22].

Historically, scientists have proposed, synthesized, and tested new molecules, often inspired by natural products or discovered by chance [52, 80]. The chemical space for potential small-molecule drug candidates is estimated to exceed 10^{60} [11], making exhaustive searching infeasible. Only a tiny fraction of this space has been explored using *in vitro* (in glass), *in vivo* (in living), or *in silico* (computer-based) methods [86]. Developing a new drug is a lengthy and costly process, often taking over 10 years and costing more than USD 2 billion [22, 27, 97, 41]. Once a new hit molecule is identified, it undergoes extensive research and several years of clinical trials before it can be commercially available [4]. There is significant motivation to accelerate this process and reduce costs. Computer-aided drug discovery (CADD) has been used for decades, but recent advancements in computing power now allow for fast virtual screening and molecule generation [68]. These technological advancements have led many to believe that "AI and machine learning will usher in an era of quicker, cheaper, and more effective drug discovery" [27].

In a 2024 article on trends and future research directions in structural biology [28], Joshi from the University of Cambridge and co-creator of *POSECHECK*—a set of biophysical benchmarks for structure-based drug design (SBDD) models [34]—remarked that:

... for all the exciting methodology development in biomolecular modelling and design, perhaps the biggest lesson for the ML community this year should be to focus more on meaningful *in-silico* evaluation and, if possible, experimental validation.

— Joshi [28]

Joshi noted that machine learning (ML) drug discovery papers rarely include experimental validation, and that the generated molecules and their poses are often nonphysical [28].

PoseBusters is a test suite designed to assess the physical plausibility of generated molecules [14]. Buttenschoen *et al.* observed that many deep learning (DL)-based methods produce molecules unsuitable for drug development, concluding that:

The next generation of DL-based docking methods should aim to outperform standard docking tools on both RMSD criteria and in terms of chemical consistency, physical plausibility, and generalizability.

— Buttenschoen *et al.* [14]

Recently, several SBDD models employing diffusion have been proposed, including PMDM [39] and DiffSBDD [72]. Huang *et al.* [39] performed both *in silico* and *in vitro* experiments, with select generated molecules undergoing experimental validation in collabo-

ration with wet lab scientists. Many collaborators of DiffSBDD were also involved in *POSECHECK*. The experimental validation and related work on *POSECHECK* enhances confidence in the physical plausibility of the molecules generated by both PMDM and DiffSBDD.

This research will thoroughly examine the mathematical details of diffusion models, with a particular focus on the implementation of PMDM. Motivated by industry sentiment, we will assess the physical plausibility of the molecules generated by both models using the PoseBusters test suite [14]. Additionally, we will perform an *in silico* celecoxib rediscovery case study.

2 Background

During a drug discovery program, medicinal or wet lab chemists must decide which compounds to synthesize and evaluate, and these decisions can be influenced by biases. The expertise of medicinal chemists is difficult to quantify with *in silico* methods alone. Research has explored capturing this expertise by analyzing chemists' preferences and framing it as a game theory problem [17]. *De novo* drug design (DNDD) aims to generate novel molecules with specific pharmacological properties [6]. These models often involve multiple constraints and objectives to ensure that the generated molecules are 'drug-like' [58]. Molecules can be generated and evaluated according to the goals at hand. Many drug discovery pipelines now incorporate ML and AI [84].

Drug discovery is broadly classified into two approaches: phenotype-based and target-based [71]. Phenotype-based approaches test small molecules directly for their effects on biological processes of interest. Our focus is on target-based approaches, which require a protein to have a known relationship with a biological process. It is assumed that molecules binding to this protein will influence the biological process [71]. However, many drugs interact with off-target proteins, causing side effects. Efforts have been made to predict off-target binding [93]. Molecules with high binding affinity for the target can enhance drug efficacy, reduce the required dose size, and help minimize toxicity and side effects [57].

A molecule can be represented in various ways, such as its chemical formula, a graph, SMILES, SMARTS, SMIRKS, InChIKey, molecular fingerprint, point cloud, among others [7, 30, 35, 65, 81, 91]. The choice of representation affects the search space and the optimization strategies that can be taken. For string or graph-based representations, combinatorial optimization algorithms are often used, while for continuous representations, gradient-based optimization strategies are typically used [22]. The complexity of the molecule generation problem is related to the chosen representation [12]. Due to the many representations, converting between them is sometimes necessary when implementing algorithms. OpenBabel is a chemical toolbox that can convert between over 110 representations and formats [60].

Generative models aim to learn the probability distribution of molecules from samples, enabling *in silico* exploration of chemical space, understanding molecular properties, and generating *de novo* molecules [86]. Many studies focus on optimizing molecules with respect to *in silico* metrics [10], with common measures listed in Table 7. These models can

be target-conditioned by incorporating protein-ligand interactions during training [22].

There is significant flexibility in selecting molecular representations and ML model architectures. The effectiveness of an algorithm depends on the choice of molecule representation, generative model, and optimization strategy [22], with many combinations having been explored [20]. Common generative models include variational autoencoders, generative adversarial networks (GANs), normalizing flows, autoregressive models, and diffusion models [10]. Dhariwal *et al.* summarized that GANs can be challenging to train because they require careful selection of hyperparameters and regularizers [21]. Likelihood models can capture more diversity and are easier to scale and train but are usually slower, and diffusion models, as a likelihood-based approach, offer extensive distribution coverage and scalability [21]. Figure 1 from Du *et al.* [22] illustrates the broad applications of generative models, their strategies, and examples of molecular representations of various dimensions.

Figure 1: Overview of generative tasks, generative strategies, and molecular representations. Figure from Du *et al.* [22].

Physical and chemical properties of generated molecules can be calculated or estimated, with common metrics for assessing 'drug-likeness' listed in Table 7. As generative models may produce molecules outside the training data distribution, ensuring their physical plausibility is crucial before progressing to *in vitro* studies. With the ultimate goal of developing a new drug, experimental validation in the laboratory and through clinical trials is arguably more important than *in silico* assessments [22, 28].

3 Diffusion Generative Models

Diffusion models, a class of deep generative models, have gained significant attention for their state-of-the-art performance in fields such as natural language processing, image generation, computer vision, and computational chemistry [95].

Generative models aim to approximate complex datasets, enabling learning, sampling, and inference [22]. Diffusion probabilistic models (DPMs), first developed by Sohl-Dickstein *et al.*, achieve this by incrementally destroying the data structure in the forward diffusion process and learning a reverse process to restore it [77]. The forward diffusion process transforms any data distribution into a simple distribution which is often Gaussian. The reverse diffusion process, a generative model, is trained to follow the forward trajectory in reverse. Once the model is trained, one can sample random noise as input to the diffusion model, which will then generate a novel output [16].

Three main formulations of diffusion models have been explored [95];

1. Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPMs)
2. Score-based Generative Models (SGMs)
3. Stochastic Differential Equations (Score SDEs)

DDPMs: Denoising diffusion probabilistic models are a class of latent variable models [36]. A DDPM is a parametrized Markov chain trained to produce samples that match the data distribution after a finite time or number of steps [77]. We try to learn the transitions in the reverse diffusion process. DDPMs are customized by choosing their variances in the forward process, and choosing the model architecture and Gaussian distribution parametrization in the reverse process.

SGMs: Song *et al.* [78] developed the understanding of score-based generative models (SGMs). They used the gradient of the log probability density function (Stein score function) to represent the probability distribution which can be learned by score matching and does not need a tractable normalizing constant [78].

Score SDEs: The stochastic differential equation (SDE) formulation allows for a continuum of distributions over time instead of a finite number of distributions in steps [79]. The forward process has no trainable parameters and is independent of the data. The reverse diffusion process is also a diffusion process [5] so we can obtain the reverse SDE. The reverse process can be approximated with a time-dependent neural network estimating the Stein scores [79].

There have been many variations of the diffusion framework. While most diffusion models use Gaussian distributions in continuous space, discrete diffusion models were introduced by Sohl-Dickstein *et al.* [77] using the Binomial distribution, with Hoogeboom *et al.* [37] later introducing Multinomial diffusion. It is also possible to use an encoder and decoder to perform Gaussian diffusion on discrete inputs and outputs using a latent diffusion model as done by Rombach *et al.* [67].

4 Related Models

Many generative models for *de novo* drug design have been proposed, with several incorporating the diffusion model framework. In addition to PMDM and DiffSBDD, which we will explore in detail, we present a sample of other diffusion-based models from the literature.

Figure 2: Examples of generating molecules in three different protein pockets for structure-based drug design. Molecules generated with DiffSBDD.

DiffDock is a generative model for molecular docking [19]. Molecular docking predicts a molecule’s position, orientation, and conformation relative to a target protein. Traditional methods seek a global optimal of the scoring function to estimate the pose. DiffDock transforms this problem into a generative modelling problem by learning the distribution of ligand poses using a diffusion process [19].

EDM (E(3)-Equivariant Diffusion Model) is designed to handle categorical atom types and their 3-dimensional coordinates [38]. Instead of using integer representations that introduce bias, it employs a one-hot encoder for atom element types. Recognizing that molecules possess translational, rotational, and some reflective symmetries, EDM generates 3D molecules without the need to order atoms, unlike autoregressive methods, and can be trained efficiently [38].

GeoLDM (Geometric Latent Diffusion Model) [94] encodes molecular geometry into a lower-dimensional continuous latent space ensuring rotational and translational equivariance, then performs diffusion in this latent space before decoding. Having integer atom representations, categorical charges and bonds, and continuous coordinate variables makes Gaussian Diffusion sub-optimal as noted by Hooigeboom *et al.* [38]. By working in a continuous latent space, Xu *et al.* circumvent the issue with non-continuous data [94].

MDM (Molecular Diffusion Model) [40], the precursor to PMDM, generates 3-dimensional molecules while accounting for atomic forces. It uses two thresholds to model molecular forces: pairs of atoms within the first threshold receive a local edge for covalent bonds, and pairs within the range of both thresholds receive a global edge for van der Waals forces [40]. Equivariant encoders are used to determine these forces and construct bonds.

TargetDiff is a DDPM equivariant method for target-aware molecule generation [32]. It uses an SE(3)-equivariant neural network to model jointly categorical atom element and their 3-dimensional continuous coordinates. The model outputs atom coordinates, with OpenBabel used to join atoms with bonds and create the molecule. Guan *et al.* suggested that incorporating bonds into the diffusion process could improve the model [32].

5 Diffusion Models for Structure-Based Drug Design

The mathematical foundations of PMDM and DiffSBDD are similar. As the architecture of PMDM is more involved, we will focus on PMDM in the following sections and then highlight the different choices made by Schneuing *et al.* for DiffSBDD.

Using the notation of Huang *et al.* in PMDM [39], alongside the concepts from Sohl-Dickstein *et al.* [77], Ho *et al.* [36], and Song *et al.* [78], we will provide a detailed presentation of the diffusion model.

5.1 Goal and Architecture of PMDM

Huang *et al.* developed the Pocket-based Molecular Diffusion Model (PMDM), a conditional diffusion framework for generating 3-dimensional molecules conditioned on a target protein [39]. This SBDD approach aims to produce molecules with high binding affinity by leveraging protein pocket information.

Figure 3: PMDM architecture. Figure from Huang *et al.* [39].

PMDM is a diffusion model where Gaussian noise is iteratively added in the forward process, and the model learns to remove this noise in the reverse process. An invariant encoder, SchNet [74] is employed to create semantic representations of the protein and ligand which are merged through cross-attention. Molecular dynamics on two scales are accounted for by constructing two classes of edges: local and global. Following the SGM diffusion interpretation of Song *et al.* [78], a dual equivariant encoder computes a score s_{θ} . Once the model’s parameters are optimized, we can generate new molecules in a target protein pocket by sampling Gaussian noise which is iteratively refined T times to produce a new ligand G_0^L . See Figure 3 for the PMDM architecture.

5.2 Notation

The ligand and protein pocket are represented as 3-dimensional point clouds $\mathbf{G} = (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r})$. The atom elements and their positions are represented as follows:

- Elements are indicated by $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in [0, 1]^{n \times s}$ using one-hot encoding, and s is the number of elements supported by the model.
- The 3-dimensional coordinates of each atom are represented as $\mathbf{r} = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 3}$.

With $\mathbf{G}^L = (\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$ for the ligand and $\mathbf{G}^P = (\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$ for the target protein pocket.

Following Sohl-Dickstein *et al.* [77], we define two Markov chains:

1. Forward/Diffusion Process: Gaussian noise is gradually added according to a pre-defined variance schedule.
2. Reverse/Denoising Process: the noise is removed to reconstruct the original ligand with high fidelity.

During the diffusion process, we obtain a sequence of latent ligands \mathbf{G}_t^L for $t = 1, \dots, T$, where t indicates the diffusion step. The protein pocket \mathbf{G}^P remains fixed as it is considered conditional information.

The reverse process is approximated by a parameterized neural network. We train the model to learn to approximate the reverse probability transition distribution. During training, the objective is to learn the optimal parameters θ that best approximate this reverse process. Empirical considerations are taken into account when constructing the objective function. New molecules can be generated conditioned on a target pocket protein by sampling \mathbf{G}_T^L from $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ and denoising \mathbf{G}_T^L through T iterations using the learned reverse process $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$.

Figure 4: Ligand diffused in pocket. Figure adapted from Huang *et al.* [39].

To simplify notation, we will first omit the conditioning on the target protein pocket \mathbf{G}^P . Later we will incorporate the protein pocket information. We can replace $q(\cdot)$ and $p_\theta(\cdot)$ with $q(\cdot | \mathbf{G}^P)$ with $p_\theta(\cdot | \mathbf{G}^P)$ respectively when conditioning of the protein.

5.3 Forward Process

The forward or diffusion process is formulated as a fixed Markov chain that gradually adds Gaussian noise over T steps. This process transforms the real data distribution towards a noise distribution, specifically $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$, where discrete time steps are denoted as $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. The forward process is not parameterized and does not involve trainable parameters θ .

It has been shown by Kingma *et al.* [48] that by increasing T the number of time steps, the variational bound improves with the finer approximation, drawing parallels to the Riemann sum approximation of the integral since as $T \rightarrow \infty$, discrete-time steps is approximately continuous.

Figure 5: Linear, cosine, sigmoid, and polynomial variance schedules. Figure inspired by Nichol *et al.* [59].

We can choose the variance schedule $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_T$ with $\beta_t \in (0, 1)$ for all t . This choice in the forward process empirically impacts the performance of the trained model [77]. Common variance schedules include linear (as employed by Ho *et al.* [36]) and cosine (as employed by Nichol *et al.* [59]). Nichol *et al.* found that in image generation, the linear noise schedule can be suboptimal. Compared to the linear schedule, the cosine schedule is designed to add noise and destroy information more slowly [59]. Nichol *et al.* found that the cosine schedule improves sampling efficiency. Using this approach, they managed to reduce sampling time from minutes to seconds for image generation by requiring fewer steps T to achieve similar sample quality [59]. The cosine schedule is designed so $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t (1 - \beta_s)$ is linearly decreasing for mid-values of t and has a slow change for t near 0 and T [59]. The sigmoid variance schedule employed by Huang *et al.* was first explored by Jabri *et al.* [44], and has even slower destruction of information than the cosine schedule. Schneuing *et al.* chose the polynomial variance schedule [72]. A comparison of these schedules in terms of $\bar{\alpha}_t$ is plotted in Figure 5.

The forward process starts at \mathbf{G}_0^L , where $\mathbf{G}_0^L \sim q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)$ is the distribution of ligands, and by making biased random steps, creates a sequence of latent representations \mathbf{G}_t^L for $t = 1, \dots, T$. At each transition between latent representations, from \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L to \mathbf{G}_t^L , the diffusion process at step t takes a random step and drifts towards $\mathbf{0}$ according to:

$$\mathbf{G}_t^L = \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t$$

where $\epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ is Gaussian noise. The predefined variance schedule $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_T$ dictates the amount of noise added through $\sqrt{\beta_t}$, and the extent the mean is shifted towards $\mathbf{0}$ through $\sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L$.

The transformation between latent representations, from \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L to \mathbf{G}_t^L , can be described as a Markov chain with the Gaussian transition distribution given by:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \beta_t \mathbf{I}) \quad (1)$$

Due to the Markov Chain formulation, we can obtain the joint distribution of the latent representations $\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L$ given the original ligand \mathbf{G}_0^L :

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) \quad (2)$$

We can find the conditional distribution of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_0^L at any step t . The conditional distribution is given by:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I}) \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t (1 - \beta_s)$.

As $\bar{\alpha}_t \rightarrow 0$, because $\beta_t \in (0, 1)$ for all t , the conditional distribution $q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ approaches $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. At time t , after sufficiently many time steps, with a well-chosen variance schedule $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_T$, \mathbf{G}_t^L is approximately pure Gaussian noise $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.

Refer to Appendix E for the proofs and explanations of Equations 1, 2, and 3.

5.4 Reverse Process

The reverse distribution $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)$ is intractable, so we approximate it with $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)$ and try to learn the optimal θ . We want θ so $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L)$ approximates $q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)$ well.

Similar to the work done by Ho *et al.* [36], see Appendix F, the distribution $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ is tractable once conditioned on \mathbf{G}_0^L , and is the following Gaussian distribution:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L), \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I}) \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) := \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \beta_t}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L \quad (5)$$

and

$$\tilde{\beta}_t := \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_t \quad (6)$$

Ho *et al.* [36] considered approximations of $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)$ with the form:

$$p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t), \Sigma_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)) \quad (7)$$

for $t = 2, 3, \dots, T$ where $\Sigma_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)$ are known values that is a chosen function of t . Huang *et al.* [39] followed the insights of Ho *et al.* [36] and chose $\Sigma_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) = \beta_t \mathbf{I}$ which is optimal if $\mathbf{G}_0^L \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. However, Ho *et al.* noted that $\Sigma_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) = \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_t \mathbf{I} = \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I}$ is the optimal choice if the initial ligand \mathbf{G}_0^L was a fixed constant but empirically both gave similar results [36].

As done by Ho *et al.* [36], the parameterization of the mean $\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)$ is inspired by L_{t-1} .

From Equation 14 we have:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL}(q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L))]$$

Both $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L), \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I})$ and $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t), \beta_t \mathbf{I})$ are Gaussian. As shown in Appendix F, we can compute their KL-Divergence and simplify to obtain the following:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \|\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2 \right] \quad (8)$$

where C is the following constant that does not depend on θ :

$$C = \frac{k}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\beta}_t}{\beta_t} - 1 + \ln \left(\frac{\beta_t}{\tilde{\beta}_t} \right) \right)$$

and k is the dimension of \mathbf{G}^L . Since C does not depend on θ , and β_t is known from the variance schedule, to minimize \mathcal{L}_{t-1} , equivalently minimize $\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C$, we should choose θ so μ_θ predicts the forward process posterior mean $\tilde{\mu}_t$ of Equation 5.

In Appendix F we show that Equation 8 is equivalent to Equation 9:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \right) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon), t) \right\|^2 \right] \quad (9)$$

From Equation 8, to minimize $\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C$, we want μ_θ to be close to $\tilde{\mu}_t$, which we now know from Equation 9 is equivalent to wanting μ_θ close to $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \right)$.

So we want μ_θ to predict $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \right)$. But at time t we know \mathbf{G}_t^L .

Following Ho *et al.* [36], we choose the parameterization of μ_θ to be:

$$\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) \right) \quad (10)$$

where ϵ_θ predicts ϵ knowing \mathbf{G}_t^L . So Equation 9 becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \right) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) \right) \right\|^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \right) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) \right) \right\|^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \right)^2 \|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{\beta_t^2}{2\beta_t \alpha_t (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)} \|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2 \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{\beta_t}{2\alpha_t (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)} \|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\sqrt{\alpha_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon, t)\|^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

If we want to sample \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L from the approximate reverse process $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)$, we would calculate the approximate mean $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta \right)$ and add the required random Gaussian noise:

$$\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) \right) + \sqrt{\beta_t} \mathbf{z}$$

where $\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.

So we can equivalently train μ_θ to predict $\tilde{\mu}_t$ or train ϵ_θ to predict ϵ . For training, we take a gradient (or stochastic gradient) descent approach to find the optimal θ . See the subsections on training and sampling for the algorithms once we condition on the protein.

5.5 Cross Entropy Objective

We chose the form of the forward process to be the Markov chain with Gaussian transitions, it has no learnable parameters. We want to find the optimal θ for the approximation of the reverse process, $p_\theta(\cdot)$, to reconstruct the training example with high fidelity.

Following the work of Sohl-Dickstein *et al.* [77] and Ho *et al.* [36], as a maximum likelihood approach is intractable, Huang *et al.* chose to minimize the cross entropy between the true distribution $q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)$ and the approximate distribution $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L)$. Using Jensen's inequality and recognizing Kullback–Leibler divergences, we can find, see Appendix G for the full derivation, that:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} [-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L)] &\leq \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\log \left(\frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \right) \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL}(q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L))] \\
&\quad + \sum_{t=2}^T \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL}(q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L))] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)]
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Breaking up Equation 12 into:

$$\mathcal{L}_T := \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL}(q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L))] \tag{13}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} := \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL}(q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L))] \tag{14}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_0 := \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)] \tag{15}$$

Equation 13 is constant as $q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ does not depend on θ and $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L)$ is Gaussian noise. Equation 14 can be minimized by training $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)$ to approximate closely $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ at every time step $t - 1$. Equation 15 can be minimized by choosing θ to reconstruct the original data with high log-likelihood given one step away.

5.6 Relation to Score-Based Generative Models

Ho *et al.* empirically found that training with Equation 16 as an objective produced better sample quality in their image generation experiments [36]. Huang *et al.* chose to adopt their methodology.

$$\mathcal{L}_{simple}(\theta) := \mathbb{E}_{t, \mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} [\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2] \tag{16}$$

Equation 16 is $\frac{2\alpha_t(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)}{\beta_t} (\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C)$ from Equation 11 to cancel the proportionality function of t : $\frac{\beta_t}{2\alpha_t(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)}$, and t for $\mathbb{E}_{t, \mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon}$ is chosen randomly from $\{1, 2, \dots, T\}$ during training.

We can now convert to the score-based generative model interpretation of diffusion from Song *et al.* [78].

From Equation 3 we have $q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I})$.

So we can write \mathbf{G}_t^L as $\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon$ where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$.

Or write ϵ as $\epsilon = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}} (\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L)$.

Using the fact that the distribution $q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ has a diagonal covariance matrix we can write its density function as:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \frac{1}{(2\pi(1 - \bar{\alpha}_t))^{k/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2(1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)}(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L)^\top(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L)\right)$$

Then find that the log density is:

$$\log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = -\frac{k}{2} \log(2\pi(1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)) - \frac{1}{2(1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)}(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L)^\top(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L)$$

Now we compute the gradient of the log density with respect to \mathbf{G}_t^L to find the Stein score function:

$$\nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = -\frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L)$$

So:

$$-\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}} = \nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = -\frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L)$$

So we could train $s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)$ to estimate $\nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ as we were going to train $\epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)$ to estimate ϵ , and they're related through $\epsilon = -\sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)$.

5.7 Incorporating the Protein Pocket Information

Huang *et al.* previously developed MDM which follows a similar framework to PMDM but does not incorporate protein information [39, 40]. The Pocket-based Molecular Diffusion Model (PMDM) is designed to generate new molecules influenced by a given protein pocket. This is a conditional diffusion model as we consider the pocket as fixed conditional information. Figure 3 shows the architecture of the model. The protein pocket's information is incorporated through its 3-dimensional structure in global edge construction, and through cross-attention in a latent representation after applying SchNet.

In the conditional setting with a known target protein pocket, we attempt to model the reverse distribution $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$ with $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$ to denoise the ligand \mathbf{G}_t^L given the protein pocket \mathbf{G}^P .

Physically, the atoms of a molecule are not restricted to a discrete grid, here the protein \mathbf{G}^P and ligand \mathbf{G}^L have continuous 3-dimensional coordinates. Traditional convolution layers would require discretizing their coordinates and information would be lost. Schütt *et al.* have proposed a continuous convolutional layer, *cfconv*, to avoid requiring grid-based coordinates, and developed SchNet, a neural network using *cfconv* layers [74]. See Figure 6 for a visual comparison of the discrete and continuous filters. SchNet learns a latent representation to predict molecular energies and atomic forces. It respects behaviour found in the physical world such as invariance to atom indexing, rotations, and translations [74].

Figure 6: Discrete and continuous convolution layers. Figure from Schütt *et al.* [74].

Huang *et al.* created latent representations for the ligand $\mathbf{G}^L = (\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$ and protein pocket $\mathbf{G}^P = (\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$ as $\mathbf{z}_L = \text{SchNet}_L(\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$ and $\mathbf{h}_P = \text{SchNet}_P(\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$ respectively.

To allow the model to focus on important protein-ligand interactions, Huang *et al.* used a scaled dot-product cross-attention to relate and combine the information from the latent ligand \mathbf{z}_L and protein pocket \mathbf{h}_P representations and output \mathbf{h}_L :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{h}_L &= \text{Cross-Attention}(\mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{h}_P) \\ &= \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d}} \right) \cdot V \\ &= \text{softmax} \left(\frac{(W_Q \cdot \mathbf{z}_L)(W_K \cdot \mathbf{h}_P)^T}{\sqrt{d}} \right) \cdot (W_V \cdot \mathbf{h}_P) \end{aligned}$$

where $Q = W_Q \cdot \mathbf{z}_L$, $K = W_K \cdot \mathbf{h}_P$, $V = W_V \cdot \mathbf{h}_P$, and d is the dimension of K [39].

Q is the query matrix, K is the key matrix, and V is the value matrix [85] so the ligand's latent representation is used to query the protein pocket latent representation and output conditioned molecular context \mathbf{h}_L [39].

Figure 7: Local and global edge construction. Figure from Huang *et al.* [39].

The ligand $\mathbf{G}^L = (\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$ and the target protein pocket $\mathbf{G}^P = (\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$ are represented by the atom element types and their 3-dimensional continuous coordinates. They are currently 3-dimensional point clouds and do not yet have bonds. To construct edges, Huang *et al.* defined a local τ_l (set at 3\AA) and a global τ_g (set at 6\AA) threshold [39]. The

edges whose lengths are shorter than the radius τ_l are local edges to represent the covalent bonds and the edges whose lengths are between τ_l and τ_g are global edges to represent the van der Waals force [39, 40]. See Figure 7 for the construction of edges.

Edges are constructed within the ligand and within the protein, but not between the ligand and protein. The pocket edge/bond information is conditional information and is determined by the target protein in question. We let 1 indicate an edge and 0 otherwise. Note that the diagonal is 0 as no self-loops/bonds are allowed. The distance between atoms i and j is denoted d_{ij} . The equivariant graph neural network will only update the A_{ligand}^l and A_{ligand}^g entries as the pocket spatial information A_{pocket}^l and A_{pocket}^g are considered fixed.

We create edges between atoms i and j as follows:

$$a_{ij} = 1 \in A^{local} \text{ if } d_{ij} \leq \tau_l.$$

$$a_{ij} = 1 \in A^{global} \text{ if } \tau_l < d_{ij} \leq \tau_g.$$

where the local threshold is τ_l and global threshold is τ_g

We store local bond/edge information as a block diagonal matrix:

$$\mathbf{A}^{local} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{\text{ligand}}^l & 0 \\ 0 & A_{\text{pocket}}^l \end{bmatrix}$$

And store global bond/edge information as a block diagonal matrix:

$$\mathbf{A}^{global} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{\text{ligand}}^g & 0 \\ 0 & A_{\text{pocket}}^g \end{bmatrix}$$

The one-hot encoded atom elements and their continuous coordinates, as well as the local edges and global edges, are inputted into local and global equivariant encoders. The local equivariant encoder models the intramolecular forces of chemical bonds. The global equivariant encoder models the long-distance van der Waals forces [39, 40].

Satorras *et al.* introduced a rotation, translation, reflection, and permutation E(n)-equivariant graph neural network EGNN which can be applied to n-dimensional spaces [69]. SE(3) includes 3-dimensional translation and rotation symmetries, and E(3) also includes reflections, so EGNN, as it is E(n)-equivariant, can be SE(3)-equivariant as this is a lesser condition. Huang *et al.* applied this EGNN to achieve SE(3) symmetries for their 3-dimensional molecules [39].

We can express this SE(3)-equivariance as $\text{EGNN}(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{G} + \mathbf{b}) = \mathbf{A}\text{EGNN}(\mathbf{G}) + \mathbf{b}$ [39] where \mathbf{A} is an orthogonal rotation matrix (its transpose is its inverse) and \mathbf{b} is a commensurable vector.

The ligand and protein structural and latent representations are:

$$\mathbf{G}^L = (\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_L = \text{SchNet}_L(\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L),$$

$$\mathbf{G}^P = (\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_P = \text{SchNet}_P(\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$$

From the latent representations of the ligand \mathbf{z}_L and protein \mathbf{h}_P , we form $\mathbf{x}^0 = [\mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{h}_P]$. From the structural representations of the ligand \mathbf{G}^L and protein \mathbf{G}^P , we form $\mathbf{r}^0 = [\mathbf{r}_L, \mathbf{r}_P]$.

Using the local \mathbf{A}^{local} and global \mathbf{A}^{global} edge matrices, and the cross-attention output $\mathbf{h}_L = CrossAttention(\mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{h}_P)$, they apply the equivariant graph neural network from Satorras *et al.* [69] in two cases, local and global, to obtain updated atom \mathbf{x}' and coordinate \mathbf{r}' embeddings:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{x}'_{local}, \mathbf{r}'_{local} &= EGNN_{local}(\mathbf{A}^{local}, \mathbf{G}^P, \mathbf{h}_L) \\ \mathbf{x}'_{global}, \mathbf{r}'_{global} &= EGNN_{global}(\mathbf{A}^{global}, \mathbf{G}^P, \mathbf{h}_L)\end{aligned}$$

Using these embeddings, found by relating latent and structural protein and ligand representations, we estimate the score function [39]. The estimated score at time step t , ultimately a function of the ligand at that time and the conditioned upon protein, is given by $s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) = [\mathbf{x}'_{local} + \mathbf{x}'_{global}, \mathbf{r}'_{local} + \mathbf{r}'_{global}]$.

5.8 Training the Model

During training, we randomly select a training sample and time step, add Gaussian noise to the training sample according to the selected time step, then predict the mean, noise, or score depending on the parametrization chosen. The loss function measures the difference between the prediction and the truth. By minimizing this loss, the network learns to reconstruct the original training sample with high fidelity, improving its ability to reverse the diffusion process.

We have found that predicting the mean, noise, and score are equivalent. Earlier we chose to use the cross-entropy objective as the loss function. Huang *et al.* incorporated the interaction between ligand and protein pocket through the cross-attention and latent representations as well as structurally. During training, we wish to learn the best θ to parameterize the reverse diffusion process. We follow the (Stein) score-based interpretation of diffusion developed by Song *et al.* [78]. The goal is to approximate $\nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$ with $s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t)$ from subsection 5.6.

Instead of:

$$\mathcal{L}_{simple}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{t, \mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} [\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2]$$

as employed by Ho *et al.*, we use:

$$\mathbb{E}_{t, \mathbf{G}_0^L} \left[\|s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) - \nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P)\|^2 \right]$$

When sampling from the diffusion model, we sample Gaussian noise and use the learned network to denoise into a new ligand. We want to do the following: $\mathbf{G}_T^L \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. So we need to translate the protein-ligand system to the origin. This is done by putting the ligand’s center of mass at time t , $CoM(\mathbf{G}_t^L)$, on the origin for every time step. We must also translate the protein, using the same translation as defined by the ligand’s center of mass.

We can adapt the training algorithm presented by Ho *et al.* [36] and clarify the algorithm of Huang *et al.* [39]. This algorithm is more involved than that of Ho *et al.* due to

the translation and the various means by which the conditional protein information is incorporated.

Algorithm 1 Training

- 1: **repeat**
 - 2: Sample a protein-ligand pair $\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P \sim q(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$
 - 3: $t \sim \mathcal{U}(\{1, \dots, T\})$
 - 4: $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$
 - 5: $\mathbf{G}_t^L = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \epsilon$
 - 6: Translate \mathbf{G}_t^L and \mathbf{G}^P so the center of mass of \mathbf{G}_t^L is on the origin
 - 7: Compute $\mathbf{z}_L = \text{SCHNET}_L(\mathbf{G}_t^L)$ and $\mathbf{h}_P = \text{SCHNET}_P(\mathbf{G}^P)$
 - 8: Compute $\mathbf{h}_L = \text{CrossAttention}(\mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{h}_P)$
 - 9: Obtain local and global edges
 - 10: Compute $s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t)$
 - 11: Take gradient descent step on $\nabla_\theta \|s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) - \nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P)\|^2$
 - 12: **until** converged
-

5.9 Sampling

Now that the model has been trained to reverse the diffusion process, we can sample novel ligands conditioned on a target protein pocket. This will allow us to explore the chemical space *in silico*.

As $\tilde{\mu}_t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1-\alpha_t}} \epsilon \right)$ and $\epsilon = -\sqrt{1-\alpha_t} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$, we can write $\tilde{\mu}_t = \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L + \beta_t \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P) \right)$.

During training, we taught $s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t)$ to approximate the Stein score $\nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t^L} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$.

So we can approximate $\tilde{\mu}_t$ with $\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L + \beta_t \cdot s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) \right)$.

We can sample Gaussian noise $\mathbf{G}_T^L \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ and then use the learned reverse process to iteratively denoise conditioned on a protein to generate a novel ligand.

Again, we can adapt the sampling algorithm presented by Ho *et al.* [36] and clarify the algorithm of Huang *et al.* [39].

Translating the location of the generated ligand in relation to the translated target protein pocket to the same relative position in the original protein pocket was not included in the algorithm implemented by Huang *et al.* but would greatly improve its usability. See Figure 14 for examples of PMDM-generated ligands in relation to their target proteins from the RCSB PDB.

Algorithm 2 Sampling

- 1: Choose \mathbf{G}^P
- 2: Sample $\mathbf{G}_T^L \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$
- 3: **for** $t = T, T - 1, \dots, 1$ **do**
- 4: Sample $\mathbf{z} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ if $t > 1$, else $\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{0}$
- 5: Translate \mathbf{G}_t^L and \mathbf{G}^P so the center of mass of \mathbf{G}_t^L is on the origin
- 6: Compute $\mathbf{z}_L = \text{SCHNET}_L(\mathbf{G}_t^L)$ and $\mathbf{h}_P = \text{SCHNET}_P(\mathbf{G}^P)$
- 7: Find $\mathbf{h}_L = \text{CrossAttention}(\mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{h}_P)$
- 8: Obtain local and global edges
- 9: Compute $s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t)$
- 10: $\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} (\mathbf{G}_t^L + \beta_t \cdot s_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t))$
- 11: $\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L = \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P, t) + \sqrt{\beta_t} \cdot \mathbf{z}$
- 12: **end for**
- 13: Translate \mathbf{G}_0^L to respect initial coordinates of \mathbf{G}^P
- 14: **return** \mathbf{G}_0^L

The output of the sampling process conditioned on the protein pocket is a single ligand with atom elements, atom coordinates, and bonds. This ligand and the conditioned protein are then fed into QuickVina 2 for molecular docking. For this reason, it would be valuable to assess this pair using *POSECHECK*. If the model relies on docking to fix the ligand then it is little more than a fancy atom and bond generating algorithm [33].

Molecular docking is a useful tool in SBDD. It models the interactions between a ligand and a protein, helping to predict the ligand’s conformation, position, orientation within the binding site, and its binding affinity, all *in silico* [56]. The conformation and orientation of the ligand are often referred to as its pose. Since the ligand can be translated and rotated continuously, the number of potential poses is limitless. The scoring function in docking typically considers both intermolecular and intramolecular contributions, summing over pairs of atoms that can move relative to each other [82]. Docking software must therefore optimize the pose efficiently to maximize the scoring function. Much care has been taken to ensure a good scoring function and many optimization strategies have been implemented. The complexity of the search problem depends on whether the ligand and protein are both considered rigid, the ligand is flexible and but the protein is rigid, or both the ligand and protein are considered flexible [56]. When we later analyze molecules together with their target proteins, we will consider the protein as rigid. AutoDock Vina is a widely used docking program, with QuickVina 2 being a faster version [3].

5.10 Comparison with DiffSBDD

DiffSBDD and PMDM share many similarities but also have distinct differences in their approaches and implementations.

They both represent the proteins and ligands with one-hot encoded categorical atom element types and their continuous 3-dimensional coordinates. Schneuing *et al.* used a polynomial variance schedule, as opposed to the sigmoid variance schedule employed by Huang *et al.*. See Figure 5 for a comparison of schedules. Schneuing *et al.* used the

simple objective function and the noise parametrization as described by Ho *et al.* whereas Huang *et al.* used the score parametrization. Huang *et al.* used cross-attention and SchNet to make latent protein and ligand representation, neither of which was done by Schneuing *et al.* [39, 72]. Both PMDM and DiffSBDD employ the equivariant graph neural network, EGNN, developed by Satorras *et al.* [69] to ensure SE(3)-equivariance. This is useful as both models repeatedly translate the protein-ligand system to the origin in training and sampling. Schneuing *et al.* make considerations to ensure that their DiffSBDD model is not reflection invariant [72] as molecules with chirality do not possess this symmetry. Schneuing *et al.* addressed the issue of disconnected molecules by implementing a re-sampling technique that allows for forward and backward diffusion steps. We will see that DiffSBDD did not generate any molecules in fragments whereas PMDM did. Both models were trained using the Binding MOAD and Cross-Docked datasets.

A key difference is that DiffSBDD does not re-dock molecules. As multiple collaborators were involved in both DiffSBDD and *POSECHECK*, they value unaltered model outputs. Huang *et al.* used QuickVina 2 to re-dock and improve the model outputs. However, they did provide the unaltered molecules on Zenodo.

Huang *et al.* and Schneuing *et al.* considered variations on conditional sampling. Schneuing *et al.* drew parallels between sampling given a molecule fragment and inpainting for image generation [72]. Both models can be used for tasks such as scaffold hopping and linker generation. In addition to generating ligands in protein pockets, Schneuing *et al.* also trained DiffSBDD to generate protein-ligand systems. They also experimented with generating molecules in the same region of the chemical space as a seed ligand by noising it partially and then denoising it, an exploration not an optimization technique.

As PMDM is more recent, Huang *et al.* tested their model against the existing DiffSBDD model in their *Nature Communications* manuscript [39], further reinforcing the comparability of the two models.

6 Methods of Assessment

De novo molecular design aims to generate novel molecules, complementing virtual screening methods where large libraries of existing molecules are ranked by a scoring function. SBDD models generate atom types and coordinates based on the structural information of target protein pockets [7]. In drug discovery, a multi-objective field, claims of state-of-the-art performance are often based on simplified *in silico* metrics [33]. The variability in evaluation methods makes it difficult to compare the strengths and weaknesses of various models.

To address these challenges, various benchmarking and testing procedures have been developed. One approach is the Turing-style test, which evaluates the capability of methods to reproduce human concepts, replicate molecules from past drug discovery efforts, and rank both human and computer-generated ideas [13]. Another example is the 'Molecular Sets' (MOSES) benchmarking platform, which standardizes the training and comparison of molecular generative models [63].

Both PMDM and DiffSBDD are SBDD models that generate molecules in specific poses. Our initial plan was to assess the physical plausibility of the molecules generated by these two models using PoseBusters, along with other standard molecular descriptors. For PMDM, as it modifies molecules through redocking with QuickVina 2, *POSECHECK* is applicable, so we intended to also analyze their intermediate outputs with *POSECHECK*. Unfortunately, we were unable to test the PMDM-generated molecules with their target proteins as planned. Future work could involve benchmarking both PMDM and DiffSBDD using GuacaMol and comparing their performance with other models on the BenevolentAI leaderboard.

As Huang *et al.* performed wet-lab validation and Schneuing *et al.* have proven to be interested in physical plausibility through the work of *POSECHECK*, it will be interesting to see the strengths and weaknesses of the two models. See Figure 8 for a visual representation of the analysis.

Note that all molecular figures were produced using PyMol [73], and all other analysis plots were created using Seaborn [88] and Matplotlib [42]. Standard element colouring is used, but the colours for carbon and the protein will vary depending on the emphasis of the plot.

Figure 8: Analyzing the physical plausibility of the PMDM and DiffSBDD-generated molecules using PoseBusters. PB Ghost from Python package.

6.1 Drug-like Properties

Molecules that are 'drug-like' typically follow certain rules, such as satisfying the Lipinski Rule of Five (having a molecular weight less than 500 daltons, a LogP below 5, no more than 5 hydrogen-bond donors, and no more than 10 hydrogen-bond acceptors) [53]. The number of rotatable bonds is a descriptor commonly used to assess the flexibility of a molecule [15]. Given that many molecules are generated *in silico*, accurately predicting these and other molecular descriptors is essential for evaluating their drug-likeness [83].

A molecule's solubility impacts its administration route, determining whether it can be taken orally or needs to be injected [41]. The octanol-water partition coefficient, or LogP [51], is a common measure of a molecule's behaviour in oily substances and is part of Lipinski's Rule of Five. Various methods have been developed to predict LogP [83, 92].

A synthetic accessibility (SA) score is an indication of the ease of synthesizing a drug, with values ranging from 1 to 10, where higher numbers indicate greater synthesis difficulty. Ertl *et al.* developed a function to estimate the difficulty of synthesis [24]. It is this SA score that we will use in further analysis following the implementation of Fiesler of the Oxford Protein Informatics Group (OPIG) [25].

For a drug to pass through the blood-brain barrier and have an effect on the central nervous system, it has various correlated chemical requirements. These include: no more than 5 atoms of nitrogen or oxygen, a LogP between 1.5 and 2.7, a molecular weight below 400 or 450 daltons, a polar surface area (PSA) of no more than 90 Å², no more than five rotatable bonds, and a limited number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors [61]. Topological Polar Surface Area (TPSA) is a gauge for the ability of a molecule to permeate various barriers such as the blood-brain barrier, an estimate of PSA [23].

Pat Walter's Silly Walks scores a molecule between 0 and 1, with 1 representing the highest level of 'silliness'. The scoring process involves converting a molecule to its SMILES string, computing its Morgan Fingerprint, comparing it to reference molecules from ChEMBL, and then returning the silliness score. We will use this score, following the implementation by Goto [31] of OPIG, to evaluate the generated molecules.

We will later analyze various properties of generated molecules using the descriptors as discussed above as well as the quantitative estimate of drug-likeness (QED). Table 7 lists common descriptors for assessing 'drug-likeness'.

6.2 POSECHECK

Models that generate molecules in fewer than three dimensions must extrapolate to determine the pose, while generating molecules directly in three dimensions avoids this issue. Most models are evaluated using *in silico* metrics such as QED, SA, and RMSD. Many models output molecule poses and then use docking software to improve these poses [34]. However, the assessment of molecular poses solely generated by the model is frequently overlooked [33].

POSECHECK addresses this gap by evaluating the generated molecules before redocking. It assesses interaction fingerprints, steric clashes, and strain energy to determine if a model outputs atoms with minimal consideration for the target protein, relying instead on

docking software to find the optimal pose [34]. As PMDM uses redocking, *POSECHECK* is a relevant tool for analyzing its output. DiffSBDD, as it shares many collaborators to those of *POSECHECK*, does not use redocking.

6.3 PoseBusters

PoseBusters is a test suite designed to identify chemically and physically implausible ligand poses generated by protein-ligand docking and molecular generation methods [14]. Docking aims to predict protein-ligand binding modes, classic docking methods take care that their predictions are physically plausible, and the Protein Data Bank (PDB) has validation methods to assess ligand structures [14]. Despite claims of SOTA performance based on *in silico* metrics, many methods can still produce physically implausible structures. To address this, Buttenschoen *et al.* [14] proposed PoseBusters, a test suite of quality checks.

Figure 9: PoseBusters identifies physically implausible molecules. Example: molecules generated by DiffSBDD clash with proteins.

PoseBusters includes three test categories: chemical validity & consistency, intramolecular validity, and intermolecular validity. See Table 8 for the full explanations of the tests. Poses that pass all tests are deemed "PB-valid". Buttenschoen *et al.* also introduced the PoseBusters Benchmark set, which includes diverse, high-quality protein-ligand pairs. For the first and second categories of tests, Figure 15 shows molecular issues the PoseBusters test suite is able to detect for the case of PMDM-generated molecules targeting the 2RMA protein. Figure 9 shows how PoseBusters can identify implausible protein-ligand interactions such as the ligand clashing with the protein. Google's AlphaFold 3 performance was partially tested using the PoseBusters Benchmark set and v0.2.7 was used to check their predictions [2].

6.4 GuacaMol

GuacaMol is a suite of standardized benchmarks designed to evaluate models used in drug discovery. It assesses various aspects such as how well a model reproduces the training data distribution, generates novel molecules, explores and exploits chemical space, and performs optimization tasks [12]. Many models claim SOTA performances so standardized benchmarks like GuacaMol are crucial for understanding these models' strengths and

weaknesses. While it is important to generate physically feasible and plausible molecules, these constraints can limit the exploration of chemical space, creating a trade-off between plausibility and exploration. Unlike PoseBusters, GuacaMol does not specifically assess physical plausibility. Brown *et al.* noted the need for future work to develop methods for assessing the quality of generated molecules. Additionally, the GuacaMol benchmarks do not assess the efficiency or time required for molecule generation, which may allow a model to filter its output at the expense of efficiency. A leaderboard is hosted by BenvolentAI, ranking the models benchmarked using GuacaMol. For a fair comparison using GuacaMol, the creators of GuacaMol recommend that models be trained on a provided dataset. Since DiffSBDD and PMDM were not trained on this specific dataset, using GuacaMol for benchmarking would not provide a fair comparison to other models.

Taking inspiration from the GuacaMol distribution and goal-directed benchmarks [12], we will assess the two models PMDM and DiffSBDD. From the distribution-learning benchmarks, we will test for validity using PoseBusters to check sanitation and InChI convertibility. From the goal-directed benchmarks, we will take inspiration from the rediscovery and similarity benchmarks. Using DiffSBDD, we will attempt to rediscover celecoxib. Using Tanimoto similarity, we can check how similar the DiffSBDD-generated molecules are to celecoxib. We will also assess whether DiffSBDD can generate molecules with the sulfonamide functional group as this is an important feature of celecoxib [89].

7 PoseBusters Busters

PoseBusters is a valuable tool for assessing the physical plausibility of molecules generated in three dimensions [14]. It helps identify chemically inconsistent and physically implausible ligand poses. As with any tool, there are areas where improvements can be made. During the assessment of PMDM-generated molecules, an error in the PoseBusters tool was identified. The error was that molecules failed to sanitize due to their nitrogen valence being greater than permitted but these molecules would pass the PoseBusters sanitation test. This is often picked up by a NaN result on the internal energy test. Bütten-schoen commented that the issue arose when a molecule could pass RDKit's sanitization rules but could not be converted to and from an InChIKey.

InChI (International Chemical Identifier) is outputted from the open-source InChI algorithm and encodes the structure of the molecule in a string [35]. The InChI algorithm generates a string representation of the molecule whose length is associated with its complexity. The InChIKey is a 27-character hashed version of InChI as many search engines struggle with long strings [35]. The InChIKey is an identifier but has lost the chemical structure from the InChI algorithm.

It is common practice to perform sanitation to ensure that any molecules being analyzed are "reasonable". RDKit has various tools for sanitation [50] which are employed in the PoseBusters tool. The molecules in Figure 11 all had the warning: "Molecule does not sanitize: Explicit valence for atom #x N, 5, is greater than permitted" where x was the index of the atom in question. The molecules with these issues passed the PoseBusters v0.2.16 sanitation test. This implies that the sensitivity of the PoseBusters test suite could be improved. Their PoseBusters v0.2.16 test results are in Table 1.

This issue inspired the v0.3.1 of the PoseBusters test suite. The release notification and additional function to test for InChI convertibility are presented in Figure 10. The updated tool checks whether molecules can be converted to and from InChIKeys, and catches more issues that cause the internal energy of the molecule to fail to be computed.

Figure 10: PoseBusters v0.3.1 release and InChI conversion test function.

Figure 11: Molecule does not sanitize: Explicit valence for atom #x N is greater than permitted

PoseBusters Tests	Generated Molecules					
Molecule ID:	1COY_93	1JN2_67	2E24_8	2ZEN_56	3AF2_55	4IYY_71
Sanitization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
All atoms connected	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bond lengths	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bond angles	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Internal steric clash	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Aromatic ring flatness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Double bond flatness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Internal energy	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

Table 1: Molecule does not sanitize: Explicit valence for atom #x N is greater than permitted

The PoseBusters test suite is not designed to state that a PB-valid molecule, one that passes all tests, is 'good'. It is a test suite to assess the 3-dimensional geometry of molecules. It is reasonable to assume that a molecule is valid until there is a reason to doubt it, and that could be that it fails a PoseBusters test. Using PoseBusters v0.2.16, a molecule may have all True or NaN values. This is an ambiguous result as it has not failed any test nor has it explicitly passed every test.

To visually express the number of molecules that fail the chemical validity & consistency, and intramolecular validity PoseBusters tests, we use a waterfall plot. To construct these waterfall plots, we can code True as 1, False as 0, and NaN as either 0 or 1 depending on the test interpretation. We can then compute cumulative products along each row, where a row holds the test results for a molecule. A value of 1 would mean that the molecule has passed all tests up to and including that test. We can then check how many 1s are in each column, find the change between successive columns, and plot the results.

Figures 12 and 13 show the impact of using PoseBusters v0.2.16 and v0.3.1 for the PMDM-generated molecules targeting the 1JN2 and 3U5Y proteins. We can also see the effect of the NaN result coded as True or False for v0.2.16. Using PoseBusters v0.3.1, a molecule would fail a test, often InChI convertibility, before reaching the internal energy test and obtaining a NaN result. Thus separate consideration of a NaN as True or False is not needed as no ambiguous results have yet been identified using PoseBusters v0.3.1. Table 8 contains the explanation of all tests [14] updated with the new InChI conversion test.

For the 1JN2 targeted PMDM-generated molecules, using PoseBusters v0.2.16 and considering a NaN internal energy a Fail, resulted in 18 more molecules failing than if considering NaN as True, increasing the number of molecules that failed on the internal energy test from 126 to 144. PoseBusters v0.3.1 was able to catch 45 molecules that were not InChI convertible. The PoseBusters test results are correlated and the waterfall plots show tests applied sequentially. The number of molecules that fail the InChI conversion test is not the same as the reduction in the number of molecules that pass all tests. Comparing the most lenient test using v0.2.16 with a NaN considered a passed test and v0.3.1, we can see a reduction of 111 from 569 to 458 or a 19.51% reduction in PB-valid molecules.

For the 3U5Y targeted PMDM-generated molecules, we see an even more extreme impact of the updated PoseBusters test suite. 108 molecules failed the InChI conversion test, and the number of molecules that passed all tests reduced from 484 in the most lenient test to 403 when considering a NaN result a Fail and 365 when using v0.3.1, a 119 molecule or 24.59% reduction in PB-valid molecules.

We will see when analyzing the DiffSBDD-generated molecules that the PoseBusters versions will make little to no difference as the molecules are generally more PB-valid, do not fail InChI convertibility, and their internal energies can generally be computed.

(a) 1JN2, PoseBusters v0.2.16 NaN is True

(b) 1JN2, PoseBusters v0.2.16 NaN is False

(c) 1JN2, PoseBusters v0.3.1

Figure 12: Waterfall plots comparing PoseBusters test results for PMDM-generated molecules for the 1JN2 protein.

(a) 3U5Y, PoseBusters v0.2.16 NaN is True

(b) 3U5Y, PoseBusters v0.2.16 NaN is False

(c) 3U5Y, PoseBusters v0.3.1

Figure 13: Waterfall plots comparing PoseBusters test results for PMDM-generated molecules for the 3U5Y protein.

8 PMDM Assessment

Huang *et al.* evaluated their model on 100 target proteins and claim to have generated 100 molecules for each protein pocket, yielding 10,000 ligands. These generated ligands were provided on Zenodo, however, 36 were missing (see Appendix I). The molecules outputted from PMDM were then re-docked using QuickVina 2, returning, most commonly, 9 poses for each molecule. It is expected that there will be 900 poses for each target protein.

Numerous challenges were encountered when attempting to implement PMDM, including poor coding practices, disregard for reproducibility, and a lack of cooperation from the corresponding author, Huang. As a result, we were only able to analyze PMDM-generated molecules that were available on Zenodo, and without their associated target proteins. See Figure 14 for examples of the molecules obtained from Zenodo, along with their corresponding target proteins from the RCSB PDB.

Figure 14: The PMDM-generated molecules are far from their PDB target proteins.

Using the PoseBusters v0.3.1 test suite, we can assess the physical plausibility of the PMDM-generated ligands but will not consider intermolecular validity tests between ligand and protein.

We will refer to molecules by their target protein, then their ID, and in the case of those re-docked, their pose. For instance; 1JN2_48 pose 7 would be the 7th (poses are one of 1, 2, . . . , 9) QuickVina 2 pose for the molecule with Zenodo file ID 48 (all IDs are one of 0, 1, 2, . . . , 99) generated targeting the protein 1JN2.

Huang *et al.* showcased three proteins in their manuscript; 14GS, 2RMA, and 3AF2. The molecules generated for all 100 proteins were provided on Zenodo but some files were missing. Proteins 1JN2 and 3U5Y were each missing three molecule files, the most of all the targets. Due to interest in the physical plausibility of the molecules they chose to showcase, and the potential reasons that there are missing files, we will analyze in greater depth the molecules generated for these five target proteins.

Figure 15: Examples of failures that PoseBusters can detect for PMDM-generated molecules for the 2RMA target protein. Test results in Table 2.

Figure 15 illustrates that PMDM-generated molecules targetting the 2RMA protein pocket can fail all chemical validity & consistency and intramolecular PoseBusters tests. Table 2 holds the test results for Figure 15. The 'molecules' and poses were chosen to best isolate only one test failure for a clear illustration of the failures PoseBusters can detect. If a molecule fails sanitation or InChI convertibility, not all further tests are performed and the molecule may receive a NaN result for certain later tests. All 2RMA molecules that had an internal steric clash failed multiple tests thus it was not possible to find a molecule that failed only the internal steric clash test.

PoseBusters Tests	PMDM-Generated Molecules for 2RMA									
Molecule ID:	62	25	60	2	45	93	57	3	10	
Sanitization	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
InChI convertible	FAIL	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
All atoms connected	✓	✓	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Bond lengths	NaN	✓	✓	FAIL	✓	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	
Bond angles	NaN	✓	✓	✓	FAIL	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	
Internal steric clash	NaN	✓	✓	✓	✓	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	
Aromatic ring flatness	NaN	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	FAIL	✓	✓	
Double bond flatness	NaN	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	FAIL	✓	
Internal energy	NaN	NaN	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	FAIL	

Table 2: Types of PoseBusters test failures for PMDM-generated molecules targetting 2RMA for Figure 15.

Physically implausible PMDM-generated 'molecules' is not a localized problem. PMDM generates many 'molecules' with valences greater than physically possible, disconnected fragments and atoms, and strange collections of atoms and bonds that cannot be analyzed with standard cheminformatics tools. We use the term 'molecules' in quotations as there are many physical laws that these outputs do not obey. Figure 16 displays 'molecules' targetting various protein pockets, none of which are of any value in a drug discovery program. The PoseBusters test results for the molecules in Figure 16 are housed in Table 3.

We can examine waterfall plots to see which tests the PMDM-generated molecules struggle on. The sequence of the tests follows the standard PoseBusters output. Note that failing sanitation or failing InChI convertibility limits the tests performed afterward. When failing multiple tests, the plot will show the 'molecule' failing the first failed test encountered. Huang *et al.* claim to have generated 100 molecules for each protein, and QuickVina 2 returns 9 poses for each molecule, thus the number of poses to analyze is 900. Not all ligands are present so missing files are incorporated into the waterfall plots.

Figure 16: PMDM-generated "molecules". Test results in Table 3.

PoseBusters Tests	PMDM-Generated Molecules					
Molecule ID:	1JN2_16	1JN2_48	2RMA_46	3AF2_69	3U5Y_7	14GS_16
Sanitization	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	✓	FAIL
InChI convertible	FAIL	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	FAIL
All atoms connected	FAIL	FAIL	✓	✓	FAIL	✓
Bond lengths	NaN	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	NaN
Bond angles	NaN	FAIL	FAIL	FAIL	✓	NaN
Internal steric clash	NaN	FAIL	✓	✓	✓	NaN
Aromatic ring flatness	NaN	✓	✓	✓	✓	NaN
Double bond flatness	NaN	✓	✓	✓	✓	NaN
Internal energy	NaN	NaN	✓	✓	FAIL	NaN

Table 3: PoseBusters test results for Figure 16.

(a) 14GS

(b) 2RMA

(c) 3AF2

Figure 17: PMDM PoseBusters v0.3.1 test results for 14GS, 2RMA, and 3AF2.

Figure 17 shows the PoseBusters v0.3.1 test results for the 3 proteins presented in Huang *et al.*'s *Nature Communications* manuscript. See Figures 12 and 13 in Section 7 for the PoseBusters test results waterfalls for the molecules generated for the 1JN2 and 3U5Y protein pockets.

Of the five target proteins considered, between 40.56% and 72.44% of the poses pass the chemical validity & consistency, and intramolecular validity PoseBusters v0.3.1 tests. InChI convertibility and internal energy are the two tests that PMDM struggles with the most. PMDM takes little care in ensuring the physical plausibility of its outputs but can still generate many physically plausible molecules, without yet considering the target protein pocket.

We will now analyze the Silly Walks scores of the PMDM-generated molecules. This is a SMILES string-based score, SMILES strings do not encode 3-dimensional positions, and docking affects the orientation and conformation of the molecule. We will analyze the pre-docked molecules to not obtain 9 near or duplicate Silly Walks scores for the 9 poses generated by QuickVina 2 for each molecule. Figure 18 shows select silly PMDM-generated molecules. PMDM can generate "silly" molecules but none assessed surpassed 0.8 out of 1. It is unclear the behaviour of Silly Walks on disconnected sets of atoms.

Figure 18: PMDM-generated molecules with high Silly Walks scores.

9 DiffSBDD Assessment

Scheuning *et al.* demonstrated greater care for reproducibility, by providing well-documented and accessible code. Harris, Jamasb, Lio, and Blundell, all of Cambridge, contributed to both *POSECHECK* and DiffSBDD. Thus, one would expect the molecules generated to make more considerations for physical plausibility. DiffSBDD, in contrast to PMDM, does not use docking software to improve their poses. This is consistent with the sentiment found in the manuscript introducing *POSECHECK* [34].

DiffSBDD allows for choosing the protein pocket based on a reference ligand. As the specific pocket targeted by Huang *et al.* is not stated, we cannot directly compare generated molecules, only confirming that the same protein is targeted. We will choose the reference ligand: chain A and residue 210 for 14GS, and the reference ligand: chain A and residue 313 for 3AF2. Roughly following the range of the number of heavy atoms in the PoseBusters Benchmark set [14], we will attempt to generate 10 molecules with DiffSBDD over the following range of the number of heavy atoms: 10, 11, 12, . . . , 49, 50. We will allow DiffSBDD to skip generations of molecules it is struggling with for computational efficiency, see Appendix A for the code used for generating molecules over a range of heavy atoms. The pocket for 14GS is on the exterior of the protein whereas the pocket for 3AF2 is on the interior and has more constraints as illustrated in Figure 19.

The waterfall plots in Figures 20 and 21 show where the DiffSBDD-generated molecules fail the PoseBusters v0.3.1 tests. 10 of the 240 molecules generated for 14GS and 18 of the 225 molecules generated for 3AF2 failed the chemical validity & consistency, and intramolecular validity PoseBusters tests. This is 4.17% and 8.00% for 14GS and 3AF2 respectively for DiffSBDD, compared to 46.78% and 27.56% for PMDM.

Notice that no molecule examined failed the simple requirements of sanitation or InChI convertibility, and none had disconnected atoms. As we have the protein, we can also use the intermolecular validity PoseBusters tests. The major failing point of the DiffSBDD-generated molecules was they often clashed with the target protein. This is the only intermolecular test that the DiffSBDD-generated molecules fail visible in the waterfall plots. By examining closely all test results, other failed tests were identified. Due to the sequential nature of the waterfall plot and the sheer number of molecules that fail the minimum distance to the protein test, other failed tests are not visible. Harris *et al.* have also noted that diffusion models for SBDD clash with protein often and that redocking helps to reduce the severity and number of clashes [34].

We can examine some PoseBusters valid molecules generated in the 14GS and 3AF2 protein pockets, see Figure 19. DiffSBDD can successfully generate molecules for both pockets on the exterior of the protein as done by 14GS as well as generating molecules for more interior pockets as seen for the 3AF2 examples.

Figure 19: Example PB-valid DiffSBDD-generated 14GS and 3AF2-targeted molecules.

(a) 14GS PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 14GS molecular descriptors plots

Figure 20: Analysis of 14GS-targeted DiffSBDD-generated molecules.

(a) 3AF2 PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 3AF2 molecular descriptors plots

Figure 21: Analysis of 3AF2-targeted DiffSBDD-generated molecules.

The analysis of the molecular descriptors for molecules generated by DiffSBDD for the 14GS and 3AF2 proteins reveals several interesting observations. Figures 20 and 21 show descriptors, computed using RDKit [50], and the SA score and Pat Walkers’ Silly Walks score were computed following the implementations of OPIG members [25, 31]. The Silly Walks score unnormalized distributions for DiffSBDD-generated molecules targeting both 14GS and 3AF2 proteins show modes around 0.4. Despite using the same range of heavy atoms, molecules generated for 14GS tend to have lower molecular weights compared to those for 3AF2. The distributions for TPSA, SA score, Silly Walks score, as well as the numbers of hydrogen bond donors, hydrogen bond acceptors, and rotatable bonds, are visually similar between the two target proteins. Perhaps these descriptor (unnormalized) distributions are similar to those of the training dataset, suggesting that DiffSBDD can learn the distribution of the training set. Molecules targeting 14GS tend to have more aromatic rings compared to those targeting 3AF2. Molecules targeting 3AF2 have lower QED values with a right-skewed distribution. In contrast, molecules targeting 14GS have a slightly left-skewed distribution and higher, more favourable QED values.

Figure 22: Correlation between molecular descriptors for DiffSBDD-generated molecules targeting the 14GS and 3AF2 protein pockets.

We can analyze the correlation between the molecular descriptors. Figure 22 visualizes these correlations for the DiffSBDD-generated molecules targeting 14GS and 3AF2. QED, as implemented by RDKit, is a function of molecular weight, LogP, TPSA, hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, aromatic rings, and rotatable bonds [50]. Unsurprisingly, QED showed correlations to the other descriptors presented. Understandably, molecular weight is positively correlated to TPSA and SA scores, as larger molecules would generally have a larger surface area and be more complex to synthesize. Silly Walks scores appear to be mildly negatively correlated with QED. Interestingly, SA score was strongly positively correlated with Silly Walks score, suggesting that silly molecules are typically also difficult to synthesize.

10 Celecoxib Rediscovery Case Study

Inspired by the celecoxib rediscovery goal-directed benchmark of GuacaMol [12], we will test the ability of DiffSBDD to rediscover celecoxib. For future reference, note that the SO_2NH_2 group is known as a ‘sulfonamide’ [66].

Celecoxib is a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that is commonly used to treat various forms of joint pain, including osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis [75]. Celecoxib selectively inhibits cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) and does not bind strongly to COX-1, a notable property compared to other NSAIDs [89]. As a selective COX-2 inhibitor, celecoxib has been shown to have less risk of causing gastrointestinal bleeding than other NSAIDs like ibuprofen [18]. Other COX-2 selective NSAIDs, such as rofecoxib and valdecoxib, were removed from the U.S. market because they increased cardiovascular risk, leaving celecoxib as the only COX-2 selective NSAID on the U.S. market and a commonly used drug for those with joint pain and high risk of gastrointestinal bleeding [18, 29, 62, 75].

In a study on rats, Kawamori *et al.* examined the effects of celecoxib on colon tumours and found promising results for the potential of using COX-2 inhibitors to prevent colon cancer [46]. Waskewich *et al.* found that although both celecoxib and rofecoxib can similarly inhibit COX-2, celecoxib has significantly more impact on cancer cells [87].

Figure 23: Celecoxib to be rediscovered

It is possible that completely unrelated proteins can have pockets with similar attributes. Penning *et al.* observed that multiple sulfonamide-containing molecules showed selective inhibition of COX-2 [62]. Abbate *et al.* identified that sulfonamides are effective inhibitors of carbonic anhydrases (CAs)[1]. The sulfonamide group is not only an inhibitor of COX-2 but can also inhibit CAs. Weber *et al.* also found that celecoxib has an affinity for multiple members of the CA family and that the sulfonamide group, which celecoxib has, can bind to catalytic zinc [89]. Weber *et al.* noted that rofecoxib, a COX-2 inhibitor which does not have the sulfonamide group, does not bind as strongly to CAs [89]. Perot *et al.* found that celecoxib can bind to both COX-2 (6COX) and CA (1OQ5), unrelated proteins with shared pocket characteristics [64]. Therefore, when attempting to rediscover

celecoxib, we will pay particular attention to those that contain the sulfonamide group as these can bind well to both COX-2 and CAs.

We will test the ability of DiffSBDD to rediscover celecoxib and will target four proteins; 1OQ5, 3KK6, 6COX, and 7ZEJ. From the RCSB PDB, we can find that celecoxib is a reference ligand A:701 for 1OQ5, A:701 for 3KK6, and A:402 for 7ZEJ. Though on RCSB PDB, 6COX has a different reference ligand with bromine instead of CH_3 , their structures are similar and Perot *et al.* found that celecoxib can bind to 6COX [64]. This alternative reference ligand is in location A:701 and its chemical formula is $C_{16}H_{11}BrF_3N_3O_2S$ instead of celecoxib which has formula $C_{17}H_{14}F_3N_3O_2S$. 1OQ5 also has a zinc ion. It was intended to see if the DiffSBDD model could adapt to this ion, but the DiffSBDD model is not equipped to model zinc as it is not a supported element. Celecoxib is presented in Figure 23.

Celecoxib is administered orally [29], hence it must have values of various chemical attributes to allow this. From the RCSB PDB, we can find that the chemical formula is $C_{17}H_{14}F_3N_3O_2S$. Celecoxib has 26 heavy atoms and 14 hydrogens. Using DiffSBDD, we attempted to generate 100 molecules with 26 heavy atoms in each target pocket, though fewer were successfully generated. For celecoxib and showcased DiffSBDD-generated molecules, we computed various molecular descriptors and presented them in Table 4.

Property	Celecoxib	1OQ5 26	3KK6 32	6COX 61	7ZEJ 37
Molecular Weight	381.379	132.203	456.427	405.429	361.53
LogP	3.51	1.04	4.26	-0.24	2.62
QED	0.75	0.62	0.44	0.40	0.73
SA Score	2.14	2.90	5.05	4.04	2.39
Silly Walks Score	0.0	0.24	0.42	0.36	0.13
TPSA	77.98	29.46	80.39	158.82	44.81
# H-Bond Donors	1	1	3	5	1
# H-Bond Acceptors	4	2	4	8	4
# Rotatable Bonds	3	4	3	6	9
# Aromatic Rings	3	0	0	1	1
PoseBusters Valid	✓	✓	False	False	✓
Has Sulfonamide Group	✓	✓	✓	✓	False

Table 4: Molecular Properties in Celecoxib Case Study

Figure 25 shows the waterfall plot and the descriptor distributions for the 1OQ5 target protein. Note that the curve in the grid of (unnormalized) distributions is a Gaussian kernel density estimate smoother. Similar plots for the 3KK6, 6COX, and 7ZEJ targets are in Appendix J along with plots showing the correlation between descriptors and the Tanimoto similarities to celecoxib. The waterfall plot and descriptor distributions for 1OQ5 are also in Appendix J for ease of comparison.

We aimed to generate 100 molecules for the 1OQ5 protein pocket for which celecoxib is known to bind, but the model returned only 68 molecules. Out of these, five molecules failed the PoseBusters tests before any intermolecular interactions with the protein were

considered. Among the generated molecules, 25 contained the sulfonamide group, a key feature of celecoxib. Two molecules passed all PoseBusters tests. This issue is consistent with what was observed in Section 9, where DiffSBDD had difficulty generating molecules that do not clash with the protein. Redocking could potentially improve this but fixing outputs retroactively is not a clear representation of the model's abilities. One molecule was in both sets, containing the sulfonamide group and is PB-valid, this is the molecule, ID #26, chosen to highlight. See Figure 24 for the selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule alongside celecoxib in the targeted pocket.

Targeting 1OQ5, DiffSBDD can generate molecules with properties that are roughly similar to those of celecoxib. The distributions in Figure 25 nearly cover all the properties of celecoxib. However, it did not generate all the features of celecoxib at the same time. DiffSBDD failed to generate molecules with the correct number of aromatic rings, generating molecules with 0 or 1 aromatic ring, which is less than the 3 aromatic rings found in celecoxib. While the mode of the molecular weight distribution for the generated molecules is close to that of celecoxib, the molecule showcased in Figure 24 and Table 4 had a significantly lower molecular weight.

Figure 24: Celecoxib and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 1OQ5

For the molecules targeting the 3KK6 protein with 26 heavy atoms, 88 were successfully generated, one molecule contained the sulfonamide group, and three others passed all PoseBusters tests (see Figure 31). We decided to present the molecule with the sulfonamide group, see Figure 26.

For the 6COX pocket, none of the molecules passed all PoseBusters tests (see Figure 32). However, two molecules contained sulfonamide groups. Both sulfonamide-containing molecules had similar properties in terms of molecular weight, LogP, QED, TPSA, and hydrogen bond donors and acceptors. We chose to present, see Figure 27, the molecule with the lower SA and Silly Walks scores, fewer rotatable bonds, and an aromatic ring.

Again we generated molecules with 26 heavy atoms but now targeting the 7ZEJ protein pocket. None of the molecules contained sulfonamide groups. After filtering for

(a) 1OQ5 rediscovery PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 10Q5 rediscovery molecular descriptors plots

Figure 25: Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 1OQ5 protein pocket

(a) Celecoxib in 3KK6 pocket

(b) DiffSBDD-generated in 3KK6 pocket

Figure 26: Celecoxib and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 3KK6

(a) $C_{16}H_{11}BrF_3N_3O_2S$ in 6COX pocket

(b) DiffSBDD-generated in 6COX pocket

Figure 27: $C_{16}H_{11}BrF_3N_3O_2S$ and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 6COX

PoseBusters-valid molecules, we obtained seven candidates (see Figure 33). Among these, the molecule with ID #37 had the lowest Silly Walks and SA scores, the highest QED, and properties similar to celecoxib, including molecular weight, LogP, and the number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors. However, this molecule had many more rotatable bonds and did not include the sulfonamide group. Figure 28 displays this molecule alongside celecoxib in the 7ZEJ pocket.

Figure 28: Celecoxib and selected DiffSBDD-generated molecule for 7ZEJ

We computed the Tanimoto index, a fingerprint-based similarity measure [8, 55], to compare the DiffSBDD-generated molecules with celecoxib. Bajusz *et al.* found that the Tanimoto index performed well along with other similarity measures such as the Dice Index, Cosine coefficient, and Soergel distance, and was superior to those based on Euclidean or Manhattan distances [8]. However, some researchers argue that Tanimoto similarity may not always be the most effective for comparing molecular fingerprints [96]. Regardless, we used the Tanimoto similarity on Morgan Fingerprints with a radius of 2 and 1024 bits, as commonly implemented in RDKit [50]. Figure 29 in Appendix J shows that all generated molecules had very low Tanimoto similarity scores. To ensure the function was implemented correctly, we verified that the similarity of celecoxib to itself was 1, as expected. It could be valuable to explore alternative similarity measures, such as the Shape and Color Similarity Score from RDKit as used in the MolSnapper manuscript [98].

From Figure 34 in Appendix J, we observe that SA and Silly Walks scores are strongly positively correlated. TPSA shows a negative correlation with both QED and LogP. For the 7ZEJ protein pocket, LogP and QED are moderately positively correlated, for 1OQ5 and 6COX, the correlation is weakly positive, and for 3KK6, there is a very faint negative correlation. From the waterfall plots in Appendix J, only five molecules fail the chemical validity & consistency, and intramolecular validity PoseBusters tests for the proteins 1OQ5, 6COX, and 7ZEJ, while only two fail for 3KK6. The primary weakness of the DiffSBDD model is the minimum distance to the protein test with the majority of molecules failing to be PB-valid.

11 Discussion

This research has evaluated two diffusion models for structure-based drug design. Though PMDM and DiffSBDD share mathematical foundations, their performances differ drastically. Both models claimed to outperform state-of-the-art methods [39, 72] and both had severe failure points.

PMDM had major usability issues. Package dependencies, missing files, hard-written file paths, and documentation in two languages all show that the code was not designed for further use. This lack of attention to reproducibility is reflected in the inaccuracies and errors found in Huang *et al.*'s manuscript published in *Nature Communications*. PMDM generated many problematic molecules, many of which do not meet the basic requirements for RDKit and InChI sanitation and contained disconnected atoms. The high PoseBusters failure rate and difficulty in implementing the code resulted in this model being of little to no value. Huang *et al.* wrote a function 'obey_lipinski' to ensure that their generated molecules would pass all of Lipinski's rules of thumb. We could similarly implement a function 'obey_posebusters'. Any generative model can be filtered retroactively. It adds no value to artificially improve PoseBusters test results by implementing a PoseBusters filter which would trivially improve the PoseBusters test performance at the expense of the time required to generate molecules.

DiffSBDD generates many PB-valid molecules without considering the protein. All molecules generated passed the basic sanitation, InChI convertibility, and connected atoms checks. However, once also considering the protein, DiffSBDD struggles to generate molecules at proper distances from the protein. Most molecules fail to be PB-valid due to clashing with the protein. DiffSBDD's code is well-designed and simple to implement. As DiffSBDD currently does not handle less common elements like zinc, an issue when we targeted 1OQ5, we could extend the model to support more elements. The model's weakness in clashing with the protein highlights an area for future work. There are multiple avenues that could be explored to address this issue.

This research has inspired an update to the PoseBusters test suite. While analyzing the PMDM-generated molecules, we encountered some unusual results with the PoseBusters test suite. These issues resulted in adding an InChI convertibility test and the release of PoseBusters v0.3.1. This update had a major impact on the number of problematic molecules identified when looking at the PMDM-generated molecules but a minimal impact on the generally more valid DiffSBDD-generated molecules. It would be useful to add another capability to the PoseBusters tool. Instead of providing a file path to a protein, it would improve workflow to add the capability inspired by PyMol to 'fetch PDBcode'.

This study has several limitations. For PMDM, we analyzed only five targets, which is just a snapshot of its outputs and we were unable to test the molecules against their targeted protein pockets. To allow fair comparison, we generated molecules using DiffSBDD for two of the proteins tested with PMDM. The specific pockets targeted by PMDM are unknown, so we can only confirm that the same proteins were targeted, not the exact pockets. For DiffSBDD, molecules were generated to have an equal number of molecules with atoms 10, 11, ..., 50. Thus, we effectively had a uniform prior on the number of heavy atoms in the molecules which may or may not be desirable. We only analyzed

the molecules it successfully generated, fewer than intended. The number of molecules that DiffSBDD did not manage to generate was not included in the waterfall plots. Due to computational constraints, we were unable to retrain PMDM and DiffSBDD on the GuacaMol-provided training set to fairly benchmark using GuacaMol. If PMDM’s reproducibility issues are resolved, it would be valuable to compare and benchmark both PMDM and DiffSBDD against a broad range of models on the GuacaMol leaderboard.

Schneuing *et al.* claimed that "DiffSBDD can generate diverse small-molecule compounds with predicted high binding affinity, outperforming state-of-the-art methods" [72]. Huang *et al.*, in their manuscript, compared PMDM to AR-SBDD, an auto-regressive model [54], and DiffSBDD for the target proteins 14GS, 2RMA, and 3AF2 [39]. They claimed that "PMDM outperforms all the baseline models on almost every metric except SA and Diversity" and that "the molecules generated by PMDM hold greater promise as drug candidates, which is crucial for clinical trials" [39]. These are strong but unsupported claims made by Huang *et al.* regarding PMDM’s performance. DiffSBDD far outperformed PMDM. Both models claim to outperform other models and generate more valuable molecules. These strong claims and less-than-stellar performances are consistent with the motivation and sentiment found in both manuscripts introducing PoseBusters and POSECHECK.

The DiffSBDD protein-ligand clashing issue leaves many opportunities to improve the model. We could try incorporating expert knowledge, as done in MolSnapper which has been shown to produce three times more PoseBusters valid molecules than DiffSBDD [98]. It would be interesting to try to improve the DiffSBDD model with Context-Guided Diffusion as developed by Klärner *et al.* who have already shown interesting results in drug discovery [49]. Another potential improvement involves using BADGER (Binding Affinity Diffusion Guidance with Enhanced Refinement) [45] which uses a differentiable network to approximate the Vina energy function which estimates protein-ligand binding affinity. By guiding the model with the gradient of this estimated Vina function, BADGER could improve DiffSBDD’s ability to generate molecules that don’t clash with the protein. We aim to generate molecules with physical constraints being the protein. We could attempt to constrain the space where generation occurs and apply techniques such as performing diffusion in this protein-constrained domain following the work of Fishman *et al.* [26]. We could also explore artificially constraining the protein pocket by expanding its surface by a tuneable number of angstroms. By generating molecules within this expanded pocket and then comparing them to the original larger pocket, we might reduce clashes. This approach would create a buffer zone, potentially allowing DiffSBDD to generate molecules that are less likely to clash with the actual protein pocket. Stability AI has developed Adversarial Diffusion Distillation [70]. Perhaps incorporating a discriminator trained to distinguish between real and generated protein-ligand pairs would yield more physically plausible ligands. These are a handful of strategies that could be explored to improve the DiffSBDD model.

12 Conclusion

We have examined two diffusion models for structure-based drug design, PMDM and DIFFSBDD. Both models claimed to outperform state-of-the-art methods [39, 72]. However, our analysis revealed severe limitations: PMDM often produces "molecules" that standard cheminformatics tools cannot work with, and DiffSBDD generates molecules that often clash with the target protein. There is considerable potential for improvement in these two models.

Consistent with current sentiment in the field [14, 28, 34], standardized assessments and benchmarking platforms are needed. As some models use docking to fix their outputs, and any model can apply a filter at the expense of time, we must take these into account to fairly compare models. We have identified, and Buttenschoen has implemented, an additional PoseBusters test which we have seen can catch a significant number of poor molecules, a small but not insignificant contribution to the field.

Future advancements in diffusion models for structure-based drug design could include integrating expert knowledge or binding affinity guidance, constraining the diffusion or protein pocket, or using a discriminator. These all aim to improve the physical plausibility of the model outputs. As the ultimate goal is to generate molecules beneficial to a drug development program, researchers ought to align their model objectives with generating physically plausible ligands that could potentially progress to wet lab evaluation.

In our *in silico* celecoxib rediscovery case study, DiffSBDD demonstrated the ability to generate molecules with some desirable properties. However, it did not manage to rediscover celecoxib with high fidelity as seen in the low Tanimoto similarity scores. A visual inspection of the most promising DiffSBDD-generated molecules and their molecular descriptors revealed some shared characteristics with celecoxib. Not many molecules were PB-valid, some had the sulfonamide group, and it was challenging for DiffSBDD to generate all properties to be similar to those of celecoxib in unison.

To reiterate, the industry needs standardized assessment and benchmarking platforms to enable comprehensive, fair, and meaningful comparisons of model performances. Claims of state-of-the-art performances on hand-picked *in silico* metrics deviate from the goal of identifying hit compounds for drug development programs. Diffusion models can generate molecules for structure-based drug design but honest and clear identification of their strengths and weaknesses is required to further advance their capabilities. Future advancements in computer-aided drug design must overcome the challenges seen in this research. Models must not only generate molecules but ensure those molecules are physically plausible, bridging the gap between *in silico* and *in vivo*, all to ultimately improve modern medicine.

Bibliography

- [1] Francesco Abbate, Claudiu T. Supuran, Andrea Scozzafava, Pierluigi Orioli, Milton T. Stubbs, and Gerhard Klebe. Nonaromatic Sulfonamide Group as an Ideal Anchor for Potent Human Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitors: Role of Hydrogen-Bonding Networks in Ligand Binding and Drug Design. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 45(17):3583–3587, August 2002. Publisher: American Chemical Society.
- [2] Josh Abramson, Jonas Adler, and Jack Dunger. Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3 | Nature, May 2024.
- [3] Amr Alhossary, Stephanus Daniel Handoko, Yuguang Mu, and Chee-Keong Kwoh. Fast, accurate, and reliable molecular docking with QuickVina 2. *Bioinformatics*, 31(13):2214–2216, July 2015.
- [4] Amy C. Anderson. The Process of Structure-Based Drug Design. *Chemistry & Biology*, 10(9):787–797, September 2003. Publisher: Elsevier.
- [5] Brian D. O. Anderson. Reverse-time diffusion equation models. *Stochastic Processes and their Applications*, 12(3):313–326, May 1982.
- [6] Kenneth Atz, Leandro Cotos, Clemens Isert, Maria Håkansson, Dorota Focht, Mattis Hilleke, David F. Nippa, Michael Iff, Jann Ledergerber, Carl C. G. Schiebroek, Valentina Romeo, Jan A. Hiss, Daniel Merk, Petra Schneider, Bernd Kuhn, Uwe Grether, and Gisbert Schneider. Prospective de novo drug design with deep interactome learning. *Nature Communications*, 15(1):3408, April 2024. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [7] Benoit Baillif, Jason Cole, Patrick McCabe, and Andreas Bender. Deep generative models for 3D molecular structure. *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 80:102566, June 2023.
- [8] Dávid Bajusz, Anita Rácz, and Károly Héberger. Why is Tanimoto index an appropriate choice for fingerprint-based similarity calculations? *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 7(1):20, May 2015.
- [9] Kelly A Berg and William P Clarke. Making Sense of Pharmacology: Inverse Agonism and Functional Selectivity. *International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology*, 21(10):962–977, August 2018.
- [10] Camille Bilodeau, Wengong Jin, Tommi Jaakkola, Regina Barzilay, and Klavs F. Jensen. Generative models for molecular discovery: Recent advances and challenges. *WIREs Computational Molecular Science*, 12(5):e1608, March 2022.
- [11] Regine S. Bohacek, Colin McMartin, and Wayne C. Guida. The art and practice of structure-based drug design: A molecular modeling perspective. *Medicinal Research Reviews*, 16(1):3–50, 1996.
- [12] Nathan Brown, Marco Fiscato, Marwin H.S. Segler, and Alain C. Vaucher. GuacaMol: Benchmarking Models for de Novo Molecular Design. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 59(3):1096–1108, March 2019. Publisher: American Chemical Society.

- [13] Jacob T. Bush, Peter Pogany, Stephen D. Pickett, Mike Barker, Andrew Baxter, Sebastien Campos, Anthony W. J. Cooper, David Hirst, Graham Inglis, Alan Nadin, Vipulkumar K. Patel, Darren Poole, John Pritchard, Yoshiaki Washio, Gemma White, and Darren V. S. Green. A Turing Test for Molecular Generators. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 63(20):11964–11971, October 2020.
- [14] Martin Buttenschoen, Garrett M. Morris, and Charlotte M. Deane. PoseBusters: AI-based docking methods fail to generate physically valid poses or generalise to novel sequences, November 2023. arXiv:2308.05777 [physics, q-bio].
- [15] Giulia Caron, Vito Digiesi, Sara Solaro, and Giuseppe Ermondi. Flexibility in early drug discovery: focus on the beyond-Rule-of-5 chemical space. *Drug Discovery Today*, 25(4):621–627, April 2020.
- [16] Ziyi Chang, George Alex Koulieris, and Hubert P. H. Shum. On the Design Fundamentals of Diffusion Models: A Survey, October 2023. arXiv:2306.04542 [cs].
- [17] Oh-Hyeon Choung, Riccardo Vianello, Marwin Segler, Nikolaus Stiefl, and José Jiménez-Luna. Extracting medicinal chemistry intuition via preference machine learning. *Nature Communications*, 14(1):6651, October 2023. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [18] Philip G. Conaghan. A turbulent decade for NSAIDs: update on current concepts of classification, epidemiology, comparative efficacy, and toxicity. *Rheumatology International*, 32(6):1491–1502, 2012.
- [19] Gabriele Corso, Hannes Stärk, Bowen Jing, Regina Barzilay, and Tommi Jaakkola. DiffDock: Diffusion Steps, Twists, and Turns for Molecular Docking, February 2023. arXiv:2210.01776 [physics, q-bio].
- [20] Suresh Dara, Swetha Dhamercherla, Surender Singh Jadav, CH Madhu Babu, and Mohamed Jawed Ahsan. Machine Learning in Drug Discovery: A Review. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 55(3):1947–1999, 2022.
- [21] Prafulla Dhariwal and Alex Nichol. Diffusion Models Beat GANs on Image Synthesis, June 2021. arXiv:2105.05233 [cs, stat].
- [22] Yuanqi Du, Arian R. Jamasb, Jeff Guo, Tianfan Fu, Charles Harris, Yingheng Wang, Chenru Duan, Pietro Liò, Philippe Schwaller, and Tom L. Blundell. Machine learning-aided generative molecular design. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 6(6):589–604, June 2024. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [23] Peter Ertl, Bernhard Rohde, and Paul Selzer. Fast Calculation of Molecular Polar Surface Area as a Sum of Fragment-Based Contributions and Its Application to the Prediction of Drug Transport Properties. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 43(20):3714–3717, October 2000. Publisher: American Chemical Society.
- [24] Peter Ertl and Ansgar Schuffenhauer. Estimation of synthetic accessibility score of drug-like molecules based on molecular complexity and fragment contributions. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 1(1):8, June 2009.

- [25] Kate Fieseler. BRICS Decomposition and Synthetic Accessibility | Oxford Protein Informatics Group, March 2023.
- [26] Nic Fishman, Leo Klarner, Valentin De Bortoli, Emile Mathieu, and Michael Hutchinson. Diffusion Models for Constrained Domains, March 2024. arXiv:2304.05364 [cs, stat].
- [27] Nic Fleming. How artificial intelligence is changing drug discovery. *Nature*, 557(7706), May 2018.
- [28] Michael Galkin. Graph & Geometric ML in 2024: Where We Are and What’s Next (Part II — Applications) | by Michael Galkin | Towards Data Science, January 2024.
- [29] Li Gong, Caroline F. Thorn, Monica M. Bertagnolli, Tilo Grosser, Russ B. Altman, and Teri E. Klein. Celecoxib pathways: pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. *Pharmacogenetics and Genomics*, 22(4):310–318, April 2012.
- [30] A Good. Virtual Screening - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics, 2007. Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry II, 2007.
- [31] An Goto. Identify Silly Molecules | Oxford Protein Informatics Group, September 2022.
- [32] Jiaqi Guan, Wesley Wei Qian, Xingang Peng, Yufeng Su, Jian Peng, and Jianzhu Ma. 3D Equivariant Diffusion for Target-Aware Molecule Generation and Affinity Prediction, March 2023. arXiv:2303.03543 [cs, q-bio].
- [33] Charles Harris. Exploring the Promise of Generative Models in Chemistry: An Introduction to Diffusion Models, July 2023.
- [34] Charles Harris, Kieran Didi, Arian R. Jamasb, Chaitanya K. Joshi, Simon V. Mathis, Pietro Lio, and Tom Blundell. Benchmarking Generated Poses: How Rational is Structure-based Drug Design with Generative Models?, August 2023. arXiv:2308.07413 [q-bio].
- [35] Stephen R. Heller, Alan McNaught, Igor Pletnev, Stephen Stein, and Dmitrii Tchekhovskoi. InChI, the IUPAC International Chemical Identifier. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 7(1):23, May 2015.
- [36] Jonathan Ho, Ajay Jain, and Pieter Abbeel. Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models, December 2020. arXiv:2006.11239 [cs, stat].
- [37] Emiel Hoogeboom, Didrik Nielsen, Priyank Jaini, Patrick Forré, and Max Welling. Argmax Flows and Multinomial Diffusion: Learning Categorical Distributions, October 2021. arXiv:2102.05379 [cs, stat].
- [38] Emiel Hoogeboom, Victor Garcia Satorras, Clément Vignac, and Max Welling. Equivariant Diffusion for Molecule Generation in 3D, June 2022. arXiv:2203.17003 [cs, q-bio, stat].
- [39] Lei Huang, Tingyang Xu, Yang Yu, Peilin Zhao, Xingjian Chen, Jing Han, Zhi Xie, Hailong Li, Wenge Zhong, Ka-Chun Wong, and Hengtong Zhang. A dual diffusion model enables 3D molecule generation and lead optimization based on

- target pockets. *Nature Communications*, 15(1):2657, March 2024. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [40] Lei Huang, Hengtong Zhang, Tingyang Xu, and Ka-Chun Wong. MDM: Molecular Diffusion Model for 3D Molecule Generation, September 2022. arXiv:2209.05710 [cs, q-bio].
- [41] JP Hughes, S Rees, SB Kalindjian, and KL Philpott. Principles of early drug discovery. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 162(6):1239–1249, March 2011.
- [42] J.D. Hunter. Matplotlib: A 2D graphics environment. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 9(3):90–95, 2007.
- [43] Les Iversen. *Drugs: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press, June 2016.
- [44] Allan Jabri, David Fleet, and Ting Chen. Scalable Adaptive Computation for Iterative Generation, June 2023. arXiv:2212.11972 [cs].
- [45] Yue Jian, Curtis Wu, Danny Reidenbach, and Aditi S. Krishnapriyan. General Binding Affinity Guidance for Diffusion Models in Structure-Based Drug Design, June 2024. arXiv:2406.16821 [physics, q-bio].
- [46] T. Kawamori, C. V. Rao, K. Seibert, and B. S. Reddy. Chemopreventive activity of celecoxib, a specific cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor, against colon carcinogenesis. *Cancer Research*, 58(3):409–412, February 1998.
- [47] Jean Kim and Orlando De Jesus. Medication Routes of Administration. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing, Treasure Island (FL), August 2023.
- [48] Diederik P. Kingma, Tim Salimans, Ben Poole, and Jonathan Ho. Variational Diffusion Models, April 2023. arXiv:2107.00630 [cs, stat].
- [49] Leo Klarner, Tim G. J. Rudner, Garrett M. Morris, Charlotte M. Deane, and Yee Whye Teh. Context-Guided Diffusion for Out-of-Distribution Molecular and Protein Design, July 2024. arXiv:2407.11942 [cs, q-bio, stat].
- [50] Greg Landrum, Paolo Tosco, and Brian Kelley. RDKit: Open-source cheminformatics., March 2024.
- [51] Albert Leo, Corwin Hansch, and David Elkins. Partition coefficients and their uses. *Chemical Reviews*, 71(6):525–616, December 1971. Publisher: American Chemical Society.
- [52] Jesse W.-H. Li and John C. Vederas. Drug Discovery and Natural Products: End of an Era or an Endless Frontier? *Science*, 325(5937):161–165, July 2009. Publisher: American Association for the Advancement of Science.
- [53] Christopher A. Lipinski, Franco Lombardo, Beryl W. Dominy, and Paul J. Feeney. Experimental and computational approaches to estimate solubility and permeability in drug discovery and development settings. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 23(1):3–25, January 1997.
- [54] Shitong Luo, Jiaqi Guan, Jianzhu Ma, and Jian Peng. A 3D Generative Model for Structure-Based Drug Design, November 2022. arXiv:2203.10446 [cs, q-bio].

- [55] Gerald Maggiora, Martin Vogt, Dagmar Stumpfe, and Jürgen Bajorath. Molecular Similarity in Medicinal Chemistry. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 57(8):3186–3204, April 2014. Publisher: American Chemical Society.
- [56] Xuan-Yu Meng, Hong-Xing Zhang, Mihaly Mezei, and Meng Cui. Molecular Docking: A powerful approach for structure-based drug discovery. *Current computer-aided drug design*, 7(2):146–157, June 2011.
- [57] Marc A. Moesser, Dominik Klein, Fergus Boyles, Charlotte M. Deane, Andrew Baxter, and Garrett M. Morris. Protein-Ligand Interaction Graphs: Learning from Ligand-Shaped 3D Interaction Graphs to Improve Binding Affinity Prediction, March 2022.
- [58] Varnavas D. Mouchlis, Antreas Afantitis, Angela Serra, Michele Fratello, Anastasios G. Papadiamantis, Vassilis Aidinis, Iseult Lynch, Dario Greco, and Georgia Melagraki. Advances in De Novo Drug Design: From Conventional to Machine Learning Methods. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(4):1676, February 2021.
- [59] Alex Nichol and Prafulla Dhariwal. Improved Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Models, February 2021. arXiv:2102.09672 [cs, stat].
- [60] Noel M. O’Boyle, Michael Banck, Craig A. James, Chris Morley, Tim Vandermeersch, and Geoffrey R. Hutchison. Open Babel: An open chemical toolbox. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 3(1):33, October 2011.
- [61] Hassan Pajouhesh and George R. Lenz. Medicinal Chemical Properties of Successful Central Nervous System Drugs. *NeuroRx*, 2(4):541–553, October 2005.
- [62] Thomas D. Penning, John J. Talley, Stephen R. Bertenshaw, Jeffery S. Carter, Paul W. Collins, Stephen Docter, Matthew J. Graneto, Len F. Lee, James W. Malecha, Julie M. Miyashiro, Roland S. Rogers, D. J. Rogier, Stella S. Yu, Gary D. Anderson, Earl G. Burton, J. Nita Cogburn, Susan A. Gregory, Carol M. Koboldt, William E. Perkins, Karen Seibert, Amy W. Veenhuizen, Yan Y. Zhang, and Peter C. Isakson. Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of the 1,5-Diarylpyrazole Class of Cyclooxygenase-2 Inhibitors: Identification of 4-[5-(4-Methylphenyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-pyrazol-1-yl]benzenesulfonamide (SC-58635, Celecoxib). *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 40(9):1347–1365, April 1997. Publisher: American Chemical Society.
- [63] Daniil Polykovskiy, Alexander Zhebrak, Benjamin Sanchez-Lengeling, Sergey Golovanov, Oktai Tatanov, Stanislav Belyaev, Rauf Kurbanov, Aleksey Artamonov, Vladimir Aladinskiy, Mark Veselov, Artur Kadurin, Simon Johansson, Hongming Chen, Sergey Nikolenko, Alán Aspuru-Guzik, and Alex Zhavoronkov. Molecular Sets (MOSES): A Benchmarking Platform for Molecular Generation Models. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11, December 2020. Publisher: Frontiers.
- [64] Stéphanie Pérot, Olivier Sperandio, Maria A. Miteva, Anne-Claude Camproux, and Bruno O. Villoutreix. Druggable pockets and binding site centric chemical space: a paradigm shift in drug discovery. *Drug Discovery Today*, 15(15):656–667, August 2010.

- [65] Shampa Raghunathan and U. Deva Priyakumar. Molecular representations for machine learning applications in chemistry. *International Journal of Quantum Chemistry*, 122(7):e26870, 2022.
- [66] Suman Rohilla and Deepika Sharma. Chapter 2 - Sulfonamides, quinolones, anti-septics, and disinfectants. In Pratap Chandra Acharya and Michio Kurosu, editors, *Medicinal Chemistry of Chemotherapeutic Agents*, pages 21–63. Academic Press, January 2023.
- [67] Robin Rombach, Andreas Blattmann, Dominik Lorenz, Patrick Esser, and Björn Ommer. High-Resolution Image Synthesis with Latent Diffusion Models, April 2022. arXiv:2112.10752 [cs].
- [68] Anastasiia V. Sadybekov and Vsevolod Katritch. Computational approaches streamlining drug discovery. *Nature*, 616(7958):673–685, April 2023. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [69] Victor Garcia Satorras, Emiel Hoogeboom, and Max Welling. E(n) Equivariant Graph Neural Networks, February 2022. arXiv:2102.09844 [cs, stat].
- [70] Axel Sauer, Dominik Lorenz, Andreas Blattmann, and Robin Rombach. Adversarial Diffusion Distillation, November 2023. arXiv:2311.17042 [cs].
- [71] Monica Schenone. Target identification and mechanism of action in chemical biology and drug discovery - PMC, April 2013.
- [72] Arne Schneuing, Yuanqi Du, Charles Harris, Arian Jamasb, Ilia Igashov, Weitao Du, Tom Blundell, Pietro Lió, Carla Gomes, Max Welling, Michael Bronstein, and Bruno Correia. Structure-based Drug Design with Equivariant Diffusion Models, June 2023. arXiv:2210.13695 [cs, q-bio].
- [73] Schrödinger, LLC. The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 3.0.3, April 2024.
- [74] Kristof T. Schütt, Pieter-Jan Kindermans, Huziel E. Sauceda, Stefan Chmiela, Alexandre Tkatchenko, and Klaus-Robert Müller. SchNet: A continuous-filter convolutional neural network for modeling quantum interactions, December 2017. arXiv:1706.08566 [physics, stat].
- [75] Sooyoung Shin. Safety of celecoxib versus traditional nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs in older patients with arthritis. *Journal of Pain Research*, 11:3211–3219, 2018.
- [76] Joram Soch. Kullback-Leibler divergence for the multivariate normal distribution, May 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4305949>.
- [77] Jascha Sohl-Dickstein, Eric A. Weiss, Niru Maheswaranathan, and Surya Ganguli. Deep Unsupervised Learning using Nonequilibrium Thermodynamics, November 2015. arXiv:1503.03585 [cond-mat, q-bio, stat].
- [78] Yang Song and Stefano Ermon. Generative Modeling by Estimating Gradients of the Data Distribution, October 2020. arXiv:1907.05600 [cs, stat].

- [79] Yang Song, Jascha Sohl-Dickstein, Diederik P. Kingma, Abhishek Kumar, Stefano Ermon, and Ben Poole. Score-Based Generative Modeling through Stochastic Differential Equations, February 2021. arXiv:2011.13456 [cs, stat].
- [80] Nicholas Ekow Thomford, Dimakatso Alice Senthebane, Arielle Rowe, Daniella Munro, Palesa Seele, Alfred Maroyi, and Kevin Dzobo. Natural Products for Drug Discovery in the 21st Century: Innovations for Novel Drug Discovery. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 19(6):1578, May 2018.
- [81] Jacob Townsend, Cassie Putman Micucci, John H. Hymel, Vasileios Maroulas, and Konstantinos D. Vogiatzis. Representation of molecular structures with persistent homology for machine learning applications in chemistry. *Nature Communications*, 11(1):3230, June 2020. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [82] Oleg Trott and Arthur J. Olson. AutoDock Vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization and multithreading. *Journal of computational chemistry*, 31(2):455–461, January 2010.
- [83] Nadin Ulrich, Kai-Uwe Goss, and Andrea Ebert. Exploring the octanol–water partition coefficient dataset using deep learning techniques and data augmentation. *Communications Chemistry*, 4(1):1–10, June 2021. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [84] Jessica Vamathevan, Dominic Clark, Paul Czodrowski, Ian Dunham, Edgardo Ferran, George Lee, Bin Li, Anant Madabhushi, Parantu Shah, Michaela Spitzer, and Shanrong Zhao. Applications of machine learning in drug discovery and development. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 18(6):463–477, June 2019. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- [85] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention Is All You Need, August 2023. arXiv:1706.03762 [cs].
- [86] Martin Vogt. Exploring chemical space — Generative models and their evaluation. *Artificial Intelligence in the Life Sciences*, 3:100064, December 2023.
- [87] Chris Waskewich, Rosalyn D. Blumenthal, Honglan Li, Rhona Stein, David M. Goldenberg, and Jack Burton. Celecoxib exhibits the greatest potency amongst cyclooxygenase (COX) inhibitors for growth inhibition of COX-2-negative hematopoietic and epithelial cell lines. *Cancer Research*, 62(7):2029–2033, April 2002.
- [88] Michael L. Waskom. seaborn: statistical data visualization. *The Open Journal*, 6(60):3021, 2021.
- [89] Alexander Weber, Angela Casini, Andreas Heine, Daniel Kuhn, Claudiu T. Supuran, Andrea Scozzafava, and Gerhard Klebe. Unexpected nanomolar inhibition of carbonic anhydrase by COX-2-selective celecoxib: new pharmacological opportunities due to related binding site recognition. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 47(3):550–557, January 2004.
- [90] Lilian Weng. What are Diffusion Models?, July 2021. Section: posts.

- [91] Daniel S. Wigh, Jonathan M. Goodman, and Alexei A. Lapkin. A review of molecular representation in the age of machine learning. *WIREs Computational Molecular Science*, 12(5):e1603, 2022.
- [92] Scott A. Wildman and Gordon M. Crippen. Prediction of Physicochemical Parameters by Atomic Contributions. *Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences*, 39(5):868–873, September 1999. Publisher: American Chemical Society.
- [93] Lei Xie, Li Xie, and Philip E Bourne. Structure-based systems biology for analyzing off-target binding. *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 21(2):189–199, April 2011.
- [94] Minkai Xu, Alexander Powers, Ron Dror, Stefano Ermon, and Jure Leskovec. Geometric Latent Diffusion Models for 3D Molecule Generation, May 2023. arXiv:2305.01140 [cs, q-bio].
- [95] Ling Yang, Zhilong Zhang, Yang Song, Shenda Hong, Runsheng Xu, Yue Zhao, Wentao Zhang, Bin Cui, and Ming-Hsuan Yang. Diffusion Models: A Comprehensive Survey of Methods and Applications, June 2024. arXiv:2209.00796 [cs].
- [96] B Zagidullin, Z Wang, Y Guan, E Pitkänen, and J Tang. Comparative analysis of molecular fingerprints in prediction of drug combination effects. *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 22(6):bbab291, November 2021.
- [97] Xiangxiang Zeng, Fei Wang, Yuan Luo, Seung-gu Kang, Jian Tang, Felice C. Lightstone, Evandro F. Fang, Wendy Cornell, Ruth Nussinov, and Feixiong Cheng. Deep generative molecular design reshapes drug discovery. *Cell Reports Medicine*, 3(12):100794, December 2022.
- [98] Yael Ziv, Brian Marsden, and Charlotte M. Deane. MolSnapper: Conditioning Diffusion for Structure Based Drug Design, March 2024.

A Select Code

The key sampling and PoseBusters steps will be outlined in the following example workflow for the 3AF2 protein.

Download the target protein from the RCSB PDB, or in PyMol do the following:

```
fetch 3af2
save 3af2.pdb
```

To use PoseBusters [14] and have the generated ligands not clash with the reference ligand defining the pocket we need to remove the reference ligand. In PyMol do the following:

```
fetch 3af2
remove chain A and resi 313
save clean_3af2.pdb
```

Generate molecules in the target protein pocket with the desired number or range of heavy atoms. See the next page for the sampling code.

We now need to get the PoseBusters test results. We do the following from the command line to check the physical plausibility of the generated molecules with respect to the target protein pocket:

```
bust 3af2_mol.sdf -p clean_3af2.pdb --outfmt csv --full-report
--output DiffSBDD_bust_3af2.csv
```

To obtain the PoseBusters test results for the PMDM-generated molecules, which are provided on Zenodo as separate files such as 3af2_87_out.sdf, in the directory containing all these files which vary by their ID from 0 to 99, we use the following command:

```
bust 3af2*_out.sdf --outfmt csv --full-report
--output PMDM_bust_3af2.csv
```

The other code is to compute descriptors, filter molecules that pass PoseBusters tests and have various attributes, and create plots. We used RDKit [50], Matplotlib [42], and Seaborn [88].

To make visuals in Pymol [73], we first choose colours, orientations, and what to show then run the following to save the image:

```
dpi=1200
ray 2000, 2000
png image_name.png
```

To generate molecules in a certain protein pocket using DiffSBDD, we run the following:

```
# Choose the name and location of the output SDF file
output_sdf_path = Path(output_dir, f'{pdb_id}_mol.sdf')

# Open the SDF writer in append mode
with Chem.SDWriter(str(output_sdf_path)) as sdf_writer:

    # Loop over num_nodes_lig values in a range
    for ligand_nodes in range(10, 51):
        num_nodes_lig = torch.ones(1, dtype=int) * ligand_nodes

        molecules_generated = 0

        # Try to generate 10 molecules for each ligand_nodes
        while molecules_generated < 10:
            print(f"Generating molecules with {ligand_nodes} atoms")

            molecules = model.generate_ligands(
                pdbfile, 1, resi_list, ref_ligand,
                num_nodes_lig, (sanitize == '--sanitize'),
                largest_frag=not (keep_all_fragments == "--all_frags"),
                relax_iter=(200 if (relax == "--relax") else 0),
                resamplings=resamplings, jump_length=jump_length,
                timesteps=timesteps)

            # Error handling
            if not molecules:
                print("Skipped this molecule")
                break
            else:
                molecule = molecules[0]

            if isinstance(molecule, Chem.Mol):
                mol = molecule
            else:
                raise TypeError(f"Error: {type(molecule)}")

            # Add the molecule to the SDF
            sdf_writer.write(mol)

            molecules_generated += 1
```

The code was built upon that of Scheuning *et al.* [72] but modified to generate molecules over a range of desired number of atoms. Previous to this code snippet are tuneable hyperparameters and methods to choose the protein pocket.

B Glossary of Acronyms and Terms

Table 5: Glossary of Acronyms and Terms

Acronym	Full Form
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	carbonic anhydrase
CADD	computer-aided drug design
COX-2	cyclooxygenase-2
DiffSBDD	Model: Diffusion Structure-Based Drug Design
DL	Deep Learning
DNDD	<i>de novo</i> drug design
DPM	Diffusion Probabilistic Model
DDPM	Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model
E(3)	translation, rotation, and reflection symmetries in \mathcal{R}^3
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
InChI	International Chemical Identifier
<i>in silico</i>	research conducted via computer
<i>in vitro</i>	Latin for "in glass"
<i>in vivo</i>	Latin for "in the living"
ML	Machine Learning
OPIG	Oxford Protein Informatics Group
PB	PoseBusters
PDB	Protein Data Bank
PMDM	Pocket-based Molecular Diffusion Model
RCSB	Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics
SBDD	structure-based drug design
SDE	Stochastic Differential Equation
SE(3)	translation and rotation symmetries in \mathcal{R}^3
SGM	Score-based Generative Model
SOTA	state-of-the-art
VLB	Variational Lower Bound

C Notation Reference Guide

Table 6: Mathematical Notation

Symbol	Description
$\mathbf{G} = (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{r})$	3-dimensional point cloud
$\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in [0, 1]^{n \times s}$	one-hot encoded atom elements
$\mathbf{r} = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 3}$	3-dimensional continuous atom coordinates
$\mathbf{G}^L = (\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$	ligand representation
$\mathbf{G}^P = (\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$	protein representation
T	number of diffusion steps
t for $t = 1, \dots, T$	index of diffusion steps
\mathbf{G}_t^L for $t = 1, \dots, T$	latent ligand representations
\mathbf{G}_0^L	initial or final ligand
\mathbf{G}_T^L	sampled Gaussian noise
\mathbf{G}^P	conditioned upon protein pocket
$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_T$	variance schedule $\beta_t \in (0, 1)$ for all t
α_t	$\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$
$\bar{\alpha}_t$	$\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s$
$\tilde{\beta}_t$	$\tilde{\beta}_t = (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})\beta_t / (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)$
θ	trainable parameters
$D_{KL}(\cdot \parallel \cdot)$	Kullback–Leibler divergence
$\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$	Gaussian distribution
$q(\cdot)$	true distribution
$p_\theta(\cdot)$	approximate distribution
$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L \mid \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$	forward transition distribution
$q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \mid \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$	true reverse transition distribution
$p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \mid \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}^P)$	learned reverse transition distribution
τ_l and τ_g	local and global thresholds
μ_θ and $\tilde{\mu}$	parameterized and true mean
ϵ_θ and ϵ	parameterized and true noise
s_θ	parameterized Stein score
$\nabla_{\mathbf{G}_t} \log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L \mid \cdot)$	true Stein score
$\mathbf{z}_L = \text{SchNet}(\mathbf{x}^L, \mathbf{r}^L)$	encoded ligand representation
$\mathbf{h}_P = \text{SchNet}(\mathbf{x}^P, \mathbf{r}^P)$	encoded protein representation
$\mathbf{h}_L = \text{CrossAttention}(\mathbf{z}_L, \mathbf{h}_P)$	fused ligand and protein information

D Table of Common Molecular Descriptors

Starting from the Table by Du *et al.* [22], we compiled a reference of common molecular descriptors and means to assess models for *de novo* drug design. The first group is a reduced set from Du *et al.*. The second set has been added.

Table 7: Common Molecular Descriptors

Metric	Definition
Validity	Percentage of viable molecules, that is, obey chemical laws.
Uniqueness	Fraction of non-repeated molecules.
Novelty	Fraction of molecules not in the training set.
LogP	Octanol–water partition coefficient that measures lipophilicity.
LogS	Logarithm of solubility.
TPSA	Topological polar surface area measuring the surface spanned by the polar atoms of a molecule (\AA^2).
QED	Quantitative estimate of drug-likeness (from 0 to 1 most 'drug-like').
Lipinski	'Rule of 5' empirical guidelines: ≤ 5 hydrogen-bond donors, ≤ 10 hydrogen-bond acceptors, ≤ 500 molecular weight, ≤ 5 LogP.
SA score	Synthetic Accessibility, a heuristic measuring synthetic complexity by scoring substructures (from easy=1 to difficult=10 to synthesize).
Diversity	Fingerprint similarity within a set of generated molecules.
Time	Assess efficiency, a function of time to generate a certain number of molecules.
RMSD	Root-Mean-Square Deviation (\AA).
Vina score	Estimates the binding free energy [82] (kcal/mol).
Molecular weight	Mass of a molecule (Da or g/mol).

E Forward Process Proofs

We want to prove that the distribution of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L is the following Gaussian distribution:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) = \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \beta_t \mathbf{I}\right)$$

Proof:

The forward diffusion process involves adding Gaussian noise to the data at each step t . This process can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{G}_t^L = \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t$$

Where the variance schedule β_t for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ is given, and $\epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ is Gaussian noise.

Since \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L is constant conditional information and ϵ_t is Gaussian, and a linear transformation of Gaussian variables is Gaussian, \mathbf{G}_t^L conditioned on \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L is therefore Gaussian.

We now only need to find the mean and variance of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L .

The mean of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L is:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L] = \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L] = \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L$$

since $\mathbb{E}[\epsilon_t] = \mathbf{0}$.

The variance of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L is:

$$\text{Var}[\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L] = \text{Var}[\sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L] = \text{Var}[\sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t] = \beta_t \mathbf{I}$$

since \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L is constant conditional information, $\text{Var}[\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L] = \mathbf{0}$.

We have found that the conditional distribution is Gaussian, and we found its mean and variance, so:

$$\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \sim \mathcal{N}\left(\sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \beta_t \mathbf{I}\right)$$

We want to prove that the joint distribution of latent ligands is the product of their conditional distributions:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)$$

Proof:

\mathbf{G}_0^L represents the original ligand. \mathbf{G}_t^L for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ are the latent ligand representations at each of the T diffusion steps. $q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)$ are the Markovian forward transition transformations distributions.

By the chain rule of probability, we can find the joint distribution:

$$\begin{aligned} q(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}_1^L, \dots, \mathbf{G}_T^L) &= q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)q(\mathbf{G}_2^L | \mathbf{G}_{0:1}^L) \cdots q(\mathbf{G}_{T-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_{0:T-2}^L)q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_{0:T-1}^L) \\ &= q(\mathbf{G}_0^L) \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{0:t-1}^L) \end{aligned}$$

where $q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{0:t-1}^L)$ is the distribution of \mathbf{G}_t^L conditioned on all previous states $\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}_1^L, \dots, \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L$.

But by the Markov property in the forward process, \mathbf{G}_t^L , the ligand at time t only depends on the ligand at time $t - 1$ \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L , so:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{0:t-1}^L) = q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)$$

The joint distribution can now be simplified to:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}_1^L, \dots, \mathbf{G}_T^L) = q(\mathbf{G}_0^L) \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) = q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)$$

By Bayes Rule we have that the conditional distribution of $\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L$ given \mathbf{G}_0^L is:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}_1^L, \dots, \mathbf{G}_T^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)}$$

But $q(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{G}_1^L, \dots, \mathbf{G}_T^L) = q(\mathbf{G}_0^L) \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)$ so we can cancel $q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)$ to get:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L) \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} = \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)$$

So, by using the Markov property and the forward diffusion process transitions, the probability of the sequence $\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L$ given the initial data \mathbf{G}_0^L is:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)$$

as desired.

We want to prove that the conditional distribution of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_0^L at any step t is given by the following:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I})$$

where $\bar{\alpha}_t := \prod_{s=1}^t (1 - \beta_s)$.

Proof:

Define $\alpha_t := 1 - \beta_t$ and $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s = \prod_{s=1}^t (1 - \beta_s)$. $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_{t-1}, \epsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$. We can use the reparameterization trick to find that we can express \mathbf{G}_t^L in terms of \mathbf{G}_0^L :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G}_t^L &= \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t \\ &= \sqrt{\alpha_t} \left(\sqrt{1 - \beta_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_{t-2}^L + \sqrt{\beta_{t-1}} \epsilon_{t-1} \right) + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t \\ &= \sqrt{\alpha_t} \sqrt{\alpha_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_{t-2}^L + \sqrt{\alpha_t \beta_{t-1}} \epsilon_{t-1} + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t \\ &= \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1}} \left(\sqrt{1 - \beta_{t-2}} \mathbf{G}_{t-3}^L + \sqrt{\beta_{t-2}} \epsilon_{t-2} \right) + \sqrt{\alpha_t \beta_{t-1}} \epsilon_{t-1} + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t \\ &= \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \alpha_{t-2}} \mathbf{G}_{t-3}^L + \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \beta_{t-2}} \epsilon_{t-2} + \sqrt{\alpha_t \beta_{t-1}} \epsilon_{t-1} + \sqrt{\beta_t} \epsilon_t \\ &= \dots \\ &= \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \dots \alpha_1} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \sum_{i=1}^t \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \dots \alpha_{i+1} \beta_i} \epsilon_i \\ &= \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \sum_{i=1}^t \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \dots \alpha_{i+1} \beta_i} \epsilon_i \end{aligned}$$

This is a linear/affine combination of $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_{t-1}, \epsilon_t$ which are all Gaussian $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.

Because linear combinations of Gaussians are Gaussian, we just need to find the mean and variance.

The mean of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_0^L is:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L] = \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \sum_{i=1}^t \sqrt{\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \dots \alpha_{i+1} \beta_i} \epsilon_i] = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L$$

since $\mathbb{E}[\epsilon_t] = \mathbf{0}$ for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$.

We will now use the independence of $\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_{t-1}, \epsilon_t$, standard properties of the variance, the definition of $\bar{\alpha}_t$, and note that \mathbf{G}_0^L is known so trivially $\mathbf{G}_0^L \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \mathbf{0})$ so we can extend the variance schedule trivially so $\beta_0 = 0$ so $\alpha_0 = 1$ and define $\bar{\alpha}_0 = 1$. Note that the notation $\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \dots \alpha_{i+1} \beta_i$ assumes that $i < t - 2$. For $i = t$ we have β_t , for $i = t - 1$ we have $\alpha_t \beta_{t-1}$, and for $i = t - 2$ we have $\alpha_t \alpha_{t-1} \beta_{t-2}$.

The variance of \mathbf{G}_t^L given \mathbf{G}_0^L is:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Var}[\mathbf{G}_t^L \mid \mathbf{G}_0^L] &= \text{Var}\left[\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L + \sum_{i=1}^t \sqrt{\alpha_t\alpha_{t-1}\cdots\alpha_{i+1}}\beta_i\epsilon_i\right] \\
&= \text{Var}\left[\sum_{i=1}^t \sqrt{\alpha_t\alpha_{t-1}\cdots\alpha_{i+1}}\beta_i\epsilon_i\right] \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^t \text{Var}\left[\sqrt{\alpha_t\alpha_{t-1}\cdots\alpha_{i+1}}\beta_i\epsilon_i\right] \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_t\alpha_{t-1}\cdots\alpha_{i+1}\beta_i\text{Var}[\epsilon_i] \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_t\alpha_{t-1}\cdots\alpha_{i+1}\beta_i 1 \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^t \alpha_t\alpha_{t-1}\cdots\alpha_{i+1}(1 - \alpha_i) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^t \frac{\bar{\alpha}_t}{\bar{\alpha}_i}(1 - \alpha_i) \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \sum_{i=1}^t \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_i}(1 - \alpha_i) \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \sum_{i=1}^t \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_i} - \frac{\alpha_i}{\bar{\alpha}_i}\right) \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \sum_{i=1}^t \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_i} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_{i-1}}\right) \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \left[\left(\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_1} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_0}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_2} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_1}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_3} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_2}\right) + \cdots + \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_t} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\right) \right] \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \left[\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_1} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_0} + \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_2} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_1} + \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_3} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_t} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right] \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \left[\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_t} - \frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_0} \right] \\
&= \bar{\alpha}_t \left[\frac{1}{\bar{\alpha}_t} - 1 \right] \\
&= 1 - \bar{\alpha}_t
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore:

$$\mathbf{G}_t^L \mid \mathbf{G}_0^L \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)\mathbf{I})$$

F Reverse Process Proofs

As found by Ho *et al.* [36], the reverse conditional distribution is tractable when conditioned on \mathbf{G}_0^L . We want to find $\tilde{\mu}$ and $\tilde{\beta}_t$ in the reverse process Gaussian transition distribution:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L), \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I})$$

The proof uses the work of Ho *et al.* [36] and Weng [90], and completed by myself.

Proof:

Recall that

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \beta_t \mathbf{I})$$

and

$$q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I})$$

so

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}) \mathbf{I})$$

With slight abuse of multivariate Gaussian notation, by applying Bayes' rule, using the Markov property, expanding the three Gaussian distributions, dropping constants of proportionality, expanding, and simplifying, we can find the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
& q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \\
&= q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \\
&= q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \\
&= q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L) \cdot q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) \cdot (q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L))^{-1} \\
&\propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\alpha_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2}{\beta_t}\right) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\right) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}\right)^{-1} \\
&= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\alpha_t} \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2}{\beta_t} + \frac{(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} - \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L - \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \right)\right) \\
&= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L)^2 - 2\sqrt{\alpha_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \alpha_t (\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2}{\beta_t} + \frac{(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2 - 2\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L + \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} (\mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. - \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L)^2 - 2\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L \mathbf{G}_t^L + \bar{\alpha}_t (\mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \right)\right) \\
&= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right) (\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L \right) \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L)^2}{\beta_t} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1} (\mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} - \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} - \frac{\bar{\alpha}_t (\mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \right)\right) \\
&= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right) (\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L \right) \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \right)\right) \\
&\quad \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L)^2}{\beta_t} + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1} (\mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} - \frac{(\mathbf{G}_t^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} - \frac{\bar{\alpha}_t (\mathbf{G}_0^L)^2}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \right)\right) \\
&\propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right) (\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L \right) \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \right)\right) \\
&= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right) \left((\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L)^2 - 2 \left(\frac{\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L}{\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}} \right) \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L \right)\right) \\
&\propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \right) \left(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L - \frac{\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \mathbf{G}_0^L}{\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}} \right)^2 \right)\right)
\end{aligned}$$

This has the form of a Gaussian distribution so by using $\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$, $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s$, and $\bar{\alpha}_t = \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}\alpha_t$ we can find the mean and variance:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\beta}_t &:= \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\right)} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\alpha_t - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}\alpha_t + \beta_t}{\beta_t(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}\right)} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1-\beta_t-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}\beta_t}{\beta_t(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}\right)} = \frac{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\beta_t \\ \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) &:= \frac{\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t}\mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\mathbf{G}_0^L}{\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}} \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t}\mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\mathbf{G}_0^L\right) \left(\frac{\alpha_t}{\beta_t} + \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\right)^{-1} \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t}\mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\mathbf{G}_0^L\right) \tilde{\beta}_t \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t}\mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\mathbf{G}_0^L\right) \left(\frac{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\beta_t\right) \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}{\beta_t} \left(\frac{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\beta_t\right) \mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \left(\frac{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\beta_t\right) \mathbf{G}_0^L \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L\end{aligned}$$

Therefore:

$$q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L), \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I})$$

where

$$\tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_t^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\mathbf{G}_0^L$$

and

$$\tilde{\beta}_t = \frac{1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\beta_t$$

as desired.

We want to prove that:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \|\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2 \right]$$

Proof:

Both $q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L), \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I})$ and $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L; \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t), \beta_t \mathbf{I})$ are Gaussian. Applying the KL-Divergence between two multivariate Gaussians [76] and inserting it into \mathcal{L}_{t-1} we find:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{t-1} &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[D_{KL} (q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)) \right] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{tr}(\beta_t^{-1} \tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I}) + (\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) - \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L))^\top \beta_t^{-1} \mathbf{I} (\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) - \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - k + \ln \left(\frac{\det(\beta_t \mathbf{I})}{\det(\tilde{\beta}_t \mathbf{I})} \right) \right) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\beta}_t}{\beta_t} k + \frac{1}{\beta_t} \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[(\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) - \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L))^\top (\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) - \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - k + k \ln \left(\frac{\beta_t}{\tilde{\beta}_t} \right) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\beta}_t}{\beta_t} k + \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{\beta_t} \|\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) - \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)\|^2 \right] - k + \ln \left(\frac{\beta_t^k}{\tilde{\beta}_t^k} \right) \right) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \|\mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) - \tilde{\mu}(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)\|^2 \right] + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\beta}_t}{\beta_t} k - k + \ln \left(\frac{\beta_t^k}{\tilde{\beta}_t^k} \right) \right) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \|\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2 \right] + C \end{aligned}$$

where C is the following constant that does not depend on θ :

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\beta}_t}{\beta_t} k - k + \ln \left(\frac{\beta_t^k}{\tilde{\beta}_t^k} \right) \right) = \frac{k}{2} \left(\frac{\tilde{\beta}_t}{\beta_t} - 1 + \ln \left(\frac{\beta_t}{\tilde{\beta}_t} \right) \right)$$

where k is the dimension of \mathbf{G}_t^L for every $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$.

Therefore

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \|\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t)\|^2 \right]$$

as desired.

We want to prove that:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) \right\|^2 \right]$$

can be written as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \right) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon), t) \right\|^2 \right]$$

Proof:

As $\mathbf{G}_t^L \mid \mathbf{G}_0^L \sim q(\mathbf{G}_t^L \mid \mathbf{G}_0^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{G}_t^L; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \mathbf{I})$, we can express \mathbf{G}_t^L as $\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) = \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon$ where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$.

We can rearrange to get $\mathbf{G}_0^L = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} (\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon)$.

Substituting \mathbf{G}_0^L into $\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) &:= \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \beta_t}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_0^L + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \beta_t}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} (\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon) \right) + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) \\ &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \beta_t}{(1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \right) \mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}} \beta_t \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t}}{(1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} \epsilon \end{aligned}$$

We will simplify this using $\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$ and $\bar{\alpha}_t = \prod_{s=1}^t \alpha_s = \prod_{s=1}^t (1 - \beta_s)$.

Note that $\bar{\alpha}_t = \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} \cdot \alpha_t = \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} \cdot (1 - \beta_t)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} + \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} &= \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} + \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)} \\
&= \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}\alpha_t}} + \frac{\alpha_t(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)} \\
&= \frac{\beta_t}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\alpha_t}} + \frac{(1-\beta_t)(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)} \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\frac{\beta_t}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} + \frac{(1-\beta_t)(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} (\beta_t + (1-\beta_t)(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} (\beta_t + 1 - \beta_t - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} + \beta_t\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} + \beta_t\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} + (1-\alpha_t)\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} + \bar{\alpha}_{t-1} - \bar{\alpha}_t) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} &= \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\alpha_t\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}} \\
&= \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \\
&= \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}
\end{aligned}$$

So

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) &= \left(\frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}} + \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_t}(1-\bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1-\bar{\alpha}_t} \right) \mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}\beta_t\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}{(1-\bar{\alpha}_t)\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}}\epsilon \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}}\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}\epsilon \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}\epsilon \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting $\tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)$ and $\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon)$, which are now in terms of \mathbf{G}_t^L and ϵ , back into:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \tilde{\mu}_t(\mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L, t) \right\|^2 \right]$$

we get:

$$\mathcal{L}_{t-1} - C = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon} \left[\frac{1}{2\beta_t} \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_t}} \left(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon) - \frac{\beta_t}{\sqrt{1-\bar{\alpha}_t}}\epsilon \right) - \mu_\theta(\mathbf{G}_t^L(\mathbf{G}_0^L, \epsilon), t) \right\|^2 \right]$$

as desired.

G Cross Entropy Proof

Following the work of Huang *et al.* [39] and Weng [90], and filling it in myself.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} [-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L)] \\
&= -\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\log \left(\int p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L) d\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L \right) \right] \\
&= -\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\log \left(\int p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L) \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} d\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L \right) \right] \\
&= -\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\log \left(\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\frac{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \right] \right) \right] \\
&\leq -\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\log \left(\frac{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \right) \right] \right] \\
&= -\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\log \left(\frac{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \right) \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{1:T}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\log \frac{\prod_{t=1}^T q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) \prod_{t=1}^T p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=1}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} + \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L) q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} + \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} + \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{t=2}^T (\log q(\mathbf{G}_t^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \log q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)) + \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} + \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} + \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_1^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} + \log q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) - \log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L) \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L)} + \sum_{t=2}^T \log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} - \log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L) \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L)} \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{t=2}^T \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)} \left[\log \frac{q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L)}{p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)} \right] - \log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L) \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} \left[\mathcal{D}_{KL} (q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L)) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \sum_{t=2}^T \mathcal{D}_{KL} (q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L)) - \log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L) \right] \\
&= \mathcal{L}_T + \sum_{t=2}^T \mathcal{L}_{t-1} + \mathcal{L}_0
\end{aligned}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}_T &:= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL} (q(\mathbf{G}_T^L | \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L))] \\
\mathcal{L}_{t-1} &:= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [D_{KL} (q(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L, \mathbf{G}_0^L) \| p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_{t-1}^L | \mathbf{G}_t^L))] \\
\mathcal{L}_0 &:= \mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [-\log p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_0^L | \mathbf{G}_1^L)]
\end{aligned}$$

as desired.

Note that Ho *et al.* [36] defined the \mathcal{L} terms as that inside of the expectations $\mathbb{E}_{q(\mathbf{G}_{0:T}^L)} [\cdot]$ but worked with the terms including the expectation. $p_\theta(\mathbf{G}_T^L) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I})$ for any θ thus Ho *et al.* did not write the θ subscript.

H PoseBusters Test Suite

Table 8: Description of the checks used in the PoseBusters test suite. Table from Butten-schoen *et al.* [14] and updated with InChI convertible test.

Test name	Description
Chemical validity and consistency	
File loads	The input molecule can be loaded into a molecule object by RDKit.
Sanitisation	The input molecule passes RDKit's chemical sanitisation checks.
InChI convertible	InChI chemistry check requiring that a valid molecule can be converted to a standard InChI key and back.
Molecular formula	The molecular formula of the input molecule is the same as that of the true molecule.
Bonds	The bonds in the input molecule are the same as in the true molecule.
Tetrahedral chirality	The specified tetrahedral chirality in the input molecule is the same as in the true molecule.
Double bond stereochemistry	The specified double bond stereochemistry in the input molecule is the same as in the true molecule.
Intramolecular validity	
Bond lengths	The bond lengths in the input molecule are within 0.75 of the lower and 1.25 of the upper bounds determined by distance geometry.
Bond angles	The angles in the input molecule are within 0.75 of the lower and 1.25 of the upper bounds determined by distance geometry.
Planar aromatic rings	All atoms in aromatic rings with 5 or 6 members are within 0.25 Å of the closest shared plane.
Planar double bonds	The two carbons of aliphatic carbon-carbon double bonds and their four neighbours are within 0.25 Å of the closest shared plane.
Internal steric clash	The interatomic distance between pairs of non-covalently bound atoms is above 0.8 of the lower bound determined by distance geometry.
Energy ratio	The calculated energy of the input molecule is no more than 100 times the average energy of an ensemble of 50 conformations generated for the input molecule. The energy is calculated using the UFF in RDKit and the conformations are generated with ETKDGv3 followed by force field relaxation using the UFF with up to 200 iterations.

Table 8 Continued from previous page

Test name	Description
Intermolecular validity	
Minimum protein-ligand distance	The distance between protein-ligand atom pairs is larger than 0.75 times the sum of the pairs van der Waals radii.
Minimum distance to organic cofactors	The distance between ligand and organic cofactor atoms is larger than 0.75 times the sum of the pairs van der Waals radii.
Minimum distance to inorganic cofactors	The distance between ligand and inorganic cofactor atoms is larger than 0.75 times the sum of the pairs covalent radii.
Volume overlap with protein	The share of ligand volume that intersects with the protein is less than 7.5 %. The volumes are defined by the van der Waals radii around the heavy atoms scaled by 0.8.
Volume overlap with organic cofactors	The share of ligand volume that intersects with organic cofactors is less than 7.5 %. The volumes are defined by the van der Waals radii around the heavy atoms scaled by 0.8.
Volume overlap with inorganic cofactors	The share of ligand volume that intersects with inorganic cofactors is less than 7.5 %. The volumes are defined by the van der Waals radii around the heavy atoms scaled by 0.5.

New test added: InChI convertible.

I Missing PMDM-Generated Molecules

PMDM target proteins:

14GS, 1A2G, 1AFS, 1AI4, 1COY, 1D7J, 1DJY, 1DXO, 1E8H, 1FMC, 1GG5, 1H0I, 1H36, 1JN2, 1K9T, 1L3L, 1PHK, 1R1H, 1RS9, 1UMD, 2AZY, 2CY0, 2E24, 2E6D, 2F2C, 2GNS, 2HCJ, 2JJG, 2PC8, 2PQW, 2RHY, 2RMA, 2V3R, 2Z3H, 2ZEN, 3AF2, 3B6H, 3CHC, 3DAF, 3DZH, 3EJ8, 3G51, 3GS6, 3HY9, 3JYH, 3KC1, 3L3N, 3LI4, 3NFB, 3O96, 3PDH, 3PNM, 3TYM, 3U5Y, 3U9F, 3V4T, 3W83, 4AAW, 4AUA, 4AZF, 4BEL, 4D7O, 4F1M, 4G3D, 4GVD, 4H3C, 4IIY, 4IWQ, 4JA8, 4KCQ, 4KEU, 4LFU, 4M7T, 4P6P, 4PXZ, 4Q8B, 4QLK, 4RLU, 4RN0, 4RV4, 4TOS, 4TQR, 4U5S, 4XLI, 4YHJ, 4Z2G, 4ZFA, 5AEH, 5B08, 5BUR, 5D7N, 5I0B, 5L1V, 5LIU, 5MGL, 5MMA, 5NGZ, 5Q0K, 5TJN, 5W2G

PMDM Missing Files:

'14gs_63_out.sdf', '1a2g_35_out.sdf', '1a2g_60_out.sdf',
'1fmc_84_out.sdf', '1h0i_33_out.sdf', '1jn2_15_out.sdf',
'1jn2_38_out.sdf', '1jn2_44_out.sdf', '1k9t_72_out.sdf',
'1l3l_6_out.sdf', '2hcj_87_out.sdf', '2pc8_10_out.sdf',
'2z3h_71_out.sdf', '2zen_41_out.sdf', '3g51_55_out.sdf',
'3gs6_30_out.sdf', '3kc1_41_out.sdf', '3li4_69_out.sdf',
'3u5y_19_out.sdf', '3u5y_57_out.sdf', '3u5y_91_out.sdf',
'4aaw_32_out.sdf', '4keu_52_out.sdf', '4p6p_3_out.sdf',
'4q8b_31_out.sdf', '4q8b_36_out.sdf', '4rlu_17_out.sdf',
'4rlu_80_out.sdf', '4rn0_78_out.sdf', '4u5s_51_out.sdf',
'5b08_68_out.sdf', '5b08_94_out.sdf', '5i0b_80_out.sdf',
'5l1v_21_out.sdf', '5ngz_79_out.sdf', '5w2g_9_out.sdf'

The number of missing files is: 36

J Celecoxib Rediscovery Plots

J.1 Tanimoto Similarity to Celecoxib Plots

Figure 29: Tanimoto similarities to Celecoxib

J.2 1OQ5 Plots

(a) 1OQ5 rediscovery PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 1OQ5 rediscovery molecular descriptors plots

Figure 30: Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 1OQ5 protein pocket

J.3 3KK6 Plots

(a) 3KK6 rediscovery PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 3KK6 rediscovery molecular descriptors plots

Figure 31: Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 3KK6 protein pocket

J.4 6COX Plots

(a) 6COX rediscovery PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 6COX rediscovery molecular descriptors plots

Figure 32: Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 6COX protein pocket

J.5 7ZEJ Plots

(a) 7ZEJ rediscovery PoseBusters waterfall plot

(b) 7ZEJ rediscovery molecular descriptors plots

Figure 33: Exploring the molecules DiffSBDD generates for the 7ZEJ protein pocket

J.6 Descriptor Correlation Plots

(a) 10Q5 correlation plot

(b) 3KK6 correlation plot

(c) 6COX correlation plot

(d) 7ZEJ correlation plot

Figure 34: Correlation between molecular descriptors